

Universities Degraded

Staff Experiences & Employer Practices
of Redundancies in UK Higher Education

June 2025

Rebecca Harrison & David Harvie

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Based on findings from the 'Survey for UCU Members on HE Redundancies',
August–October 2024.

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AUTHOR AND CONTENT NOTES

About the authors

The authors of this survey have held academic positions in English and Scottish universities. One author has gone through a redundancy process. While neither author now works in the sector, both remain active as researchers and committed to imagining more accessible, ethical, and creative possibilities for education.

Both authors have been members of UCU's elected national committees, with one holding an officer position. At the time of writing, one maintains UCU membership; the other does not. The authors' findings and analyses are based on data gathered in response to a redundancy survey created and distributed via a UCU branch in 2024.

Content warning

Please be advised that this report contains references to, and first-hand accounts of, people's experiences of ill-health, trauma, and discrimination. These accounts can be distressing to read.

Disclaimer

The survey underpinning this report sought responses from UCU members and was distributed by UCU members and staff. However, this is an independent report that has not been endorsed by UCU's officers, committees, branches, or staff in any capacity.

The authors do not purport to represent the views of UCU members, staff, or branches. The authors do not necessarily share or endorse the views of survey respondents.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank everyone who shared their story so that workers' conditions in higher education might be more widely recognised and job cuts more effectively resisted.

Thanks to everyone who worked on creating and distributing the survey, peer reviewing the report, and circulating report findings.

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GLOSSARY

These phrases and acronyms appear either in the authored report, or in appendices comprising respondents' answers to open-box survey questions.

ASOS – action short of a strike, a form of industrial action.

Casework – support provided between union members. A caseworker member might assist another member with navigating institutional processes such as grievances, victimisation, etc.

CD – course director, usually an academic/practitioner responsible for managing a specific programme of study.

CR – compulsory redundancy.

Exec – a UCU branch's elected executive committee, which is responsible for, among other things, negotiating and consulting with an institution's managers, supporting UCU members, and communicating issues to regional and national UCU officers.

FTE – full-time equivalent, a means of quantifying employee headcount and/or describing fractional (part-time) contracts. Posts can be full-time (**FT**) or part-time (**PT**).

HE/HEI – higher education, or higher education institution (usually a university).

HoD/HoS – head of department or school. A mid-managerial position usually held by an academic with a senior lecturer or professorial appointment.

MAB – marking and assessment boycott, a form of industrial action last deployed nationally by UCU in 2023.

MARS – mutually agreed resignation scheme.

NDA – non-disclosure agreement. Typically a condition of a settlement between the employer and worker when the worker leaves their employment owing to a dispute and receives a financial package. Widely criticised for their silencing nature (NDAs tend to favour employers), these legal contracts are known by a number of acronyms, including CAs (confidentiality agreements).

PL/SL – principal lecturer. An academic job role (others include assistant lecturer, associate lecturer, senior lecturer, lecturer, reader, professor, and emeritus professor). Titles vary by institution and have different responsibilities. Across all institutions, job titles indicate an employee's position in a hierarchical system.

Post-92 – a higher education institution established in or after 1992 following changes to legislation that enabled former polytechnics to gain university status. Post-92s tend to serve students who live locally to the institution, and often recruit high numbers of marginalised students (including those from economically deprived backgrounds).

REF – Research Excellence Framework, a government-mandated competition between higher education institutions at department level (e.g., History departments compete against one another across the four nations). The process involves panels of academics who have agreed to score the work of their peers to create quantitative data. The numeric scores then determine the amount of funding eligible universities are awarded by government for research activities.

Russell Group – a lobbying group of self-selecting higher education institutions. The Russell Group lobbies government for conditions favourable to its members, and successfully brands itself as 'elite' to encourage students to choose its member institutions over others outside the group.

SAR – subject access request, a personal legal entitlement to procure all data (including emails) held about you by an institution.

SMT/SLT – senior management or leadership team.

TEF – Teaching Excellence Framework, another government-imposed scheme to rank institutions. This one awards universities gold, silver, or bronze for teaching based on a number of criteria, few of which relate to the quality of pedagogy.

TUPE - Transfer of Undertakings (Protection of Employment). These regulations underpin situations whereby an employee's contract is passed from one employer to another.

UCEA – the Universities and Colleges Employers' Association, which represents higher education employers in negotiations with trade unions, government bodies, etc.

Victimisation – the unlawful targeting of an employee by their colleagues after the employee has made a complaint or been involved in whistleblowing.

VR – voluntary redundancy.

VC/PVC – vice chancellor, the university's chief executive officer equivalent. The VC is usually the highest paid employee at the institution. The pro vice-chancellor is a supporting job category on the senior management team.

VSS/VES/VL – voluntary severance scheme, voluntary exit scheme (for trade union reps), and voluntary leaver.

USS – Universities Superannuation Scheme, a pension scheme available to many workers in pre-1992 institutions.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Conducted between August and October 2024 and publicised mainly by members of the University and College Union (UCU), the 'Survey for UCU Members on HE Redundancies' invited responses from UCU members at universities where managers were implementing redundancy processes (broadly conceived) or had done in the past five years.

The findings in this report are based on 349 survey responses, spanning 97 higher education institutions.

We estimate that approximately 8,900 people are being, or recently have been, affected by compulsory redundancies across the sector's 165 institutions.

We estimate that around 11,500 people in the higher education sector are affected by 'backdoor' redundancies, such as hiring freezes, non-renewal of fixed-term contracts, voluntary severance and redundancy, protected conversations, and fire and rehire.

Unethical practice

Numerous respondents report unethical and even potentially unlawful behaviour by their employers. They allege that of the 97 institutions represented in survey responses:

73% of HEIs are failing to adequately consult with those individuals at risk of redundancy.

73% of senior management teams are failing to implement/accept suggested alternatives to redundancies.

69% of HEIs are failing to adequately consult with trade unions.

54% of senior management teams are bullying staff into applying for voluntary severance and/or voluntary redundancy.

52% of HEIs are failing to adhere to institutional policies governing redundancy processes.

45% of HEIs are failing to follow legislation governing redundancy processes.

29% of HEIs are misusing 'protected conversations' to make staff redundant.

The human cost

The impacts on staff—whether they remain in post or lose their jobs—are striking:

91% noticed a deterioration in working conditions, including less collegiality and lower morale.

90% cited emerging anxiety, stress, depression or other health problems as a result of redundancy processes.

87% said workloads for remaining staff increased when colleagues were made redundant.

76% noted worsening of existing mental health or other health problems.

36% described the undermining of academic freedom.

36% cited the targeting of people openly critical of management.

23% noticed the targeting of people with protected characteristics for redundancy.

21% alleged trade union victimisation in the selection of people targeted for redundancy.

What respondents said about their experiences:

'It felt, as a colleague said, "like watching the birth of fascism", as colleagues singled out for redundancy were isolated.'

'Sickening to see university advertising for social justice. Corruption within HE is rampant. Look at who is being protected and why.'

'Our university has given a pompous name to the process of reshaping the work and workload of who is left which — de facto — amounts to covering holes, more workload, less freedom on how to do the work (less academic freedom) and, in the end, less services for staff and students.'

'An atmosphere of fear and intimidation for any who do not toe the line. I love this university but despise its hateful, greedy and mostly incompetent leadership. If I had an option to leave, I would take it now.'

'Where is the debate and discussion and students who come for love of the subject and passion for learning? All of this has been reduced to 'customers' paying ~£9k a year to be spoon-fed job training. What is the point??? Honestly, if I could get out and switch career, I would.'

The survey questions, and respondents' open-box answers to one pertinent question, are reproduced as appendices to this report.

INTRODUCTION

From defunding and censorship initiatives implemented by successive governments, to attacks on the sector in the right-wing press, higher education in the UK faces numerous challenges.

Labour, under then-Prime Minister Tony Blair, began the commoditisation of university degrees with the introduction of tuition fees for students in England and Wales in 1998, and oversaw fee rises in 2004. Various Conservative governments (including the Conservative-Liberal Democrat coalition) increased the student debt burden—tuition-fees tripled in 2012—at the same time as they have reduced direct state funding of universities. In 2015, the government removed student number caps, which allowed universities to recruit as many UK students as they were able. Detrimental consequences have abounded, with lack of available accommodation for students at oversubscribed institutions (which has also impacted on local communities), increases in staff workloads, and bidding wars for student enrolments between institutions. University leadership teams have typically taken on more debt to fund new buildings to house additional students. The intensified competitive environment has destabilised the sector's finances across the four nations.

With many institutions increasingly dependent upon students who come to the UK from abroad (who pay far greater fees than so-called 'domestic' students), the hostile visa conditions created by a succession of authoritarian Home Secretaries have proved particularly harmful to universities' balance sheets. As universities have become more corporate, their senior managers have gutted governance structures to concentrate power among small groups of highly paid, powerful actors who are not necessarily accountable to staff or students for poor planning and financial decision making; take, for example, recent revelations about senior managers' accounting at the University of Dundee.¹ Under Keir Starmer, the current Labour administration is wilfully ignoring the crisis facing university workers and the students that they support.

That UK universities are experiencing financial crises is widely accepted by university staff, politicians, sector regulators, and the news media (although the causes of such crises are up for debate, with at least some 'crises' seemingly manufactured by senior managers to justify ideologically driven restructuring). The Office for Students, the body charged with regulating the sector in England, reported in November 2024 that almost three-quarters of English higher education institutions (HEIs) are forecast to be in deficit in the 2025/26 academic year.² Some of the most significant impacts of these financial deficits have been mass job cuts, which university managers have implemented at an unprecedented scale. They have closed whole departments and shut down entire fields of research and teaching.

Redundancy and/or restructuring are either underway, or recently have concluded, at 98 institutions across the four nations as of May 23, 2025, according to a list assembled by the Queen Mary branch of the University and College Union (UCU).³ There have been many, many others in recent years. Queen Mary UCU notes that the higher education sector 'is vital to the country's future' and calls the hollowing out of university staff 'vandalism' that is 'unconscionable'. But what do we mean when we talk about the 'higher

¹ Graeme Ogston, "Dundee University Insolvency 'A Real Possibility,'" March 19, 2025, <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/cy0520y092po>.

² Office for Students, "'Bold and Transformative Action' Needed to Address Financial Sustainability – OfS," November 15, 2024, <https://www.officeforstudents.org.uk/news-blog-and-events/press-and-media/bold-and-transformative-action-needed-to-address-financial-sustainability-ofs/>.

³ UCU Queen Mary University of London, "HE Shrinking," May 23, 2025, <https://qmucu.org/qmul-transformation/uk-he-shrinking/#current-redundancy-programmes>

education sector'? What, or whom, is being vandalised? And who should be accountable for the destruction of our universities?

The 'Survey for UCU Members on HE Redundancies', conducted online between August and October 2024, aimed to help university workers answer these questions. While we (the authors) understand the broad contours of the multiple challenges facing universities, we are unaware of much research at a more granular level that examines the impacts of financial crises (whether actual or manufactured) on university staff.⁴ This report attempts to fill the gaps in our collective knowledge by giving voice to the university workers being or made 'redundant', and to the workers supporting colleagues on the sharp end of job cuts.

The report draws on the responses of 349 university workers (and former university workers), spanning 97 HEIs, to a survey that asked questions about personal experiences of redundancies and resistance in UK universities. (You can read the survey questions in the Appendices section of this report). The survey results reveal new evidence about the scale of the problem. Based on a conservative estimate, the data suggests that around 6.7% (one in 15) of university staff are currently at risk of redundancy or have been in the past five years – and it's possible that as many as 11–12% (one in nine) are or have been.

Just as alarming as the scale of job cuts are the methods that university employers are using to undertake redundancies. According to respondents, unethical behaviour by managers appears to be the norm: at around three-quarters of institutions, respondents suggest managers are failing to adequately consult with either at-risk individuals or relevant trade unions. At around half of institutions represented in the survey, respondents report misuse of protected conversations, failures to adhere to institutional policies and government legislation on redundancies, and the bullying of staff into applying for voluntary redundancy or severance. Respondents repeatedly allege that managers exhibit behaviours (such as bullying or failure to adhere to legislation) that could be potentially be deemed unlawful if taken before an employment tribunal.

The report also explores the justifications university employers are offering for their redundancy programmes. Financial reasons and/or poor student recruitment, particularly of so-called 'international' students, were cited in almost all cases – an unsurprising finding. But a significant number of respondents also mentioned the costs associated with new campus developments and the servicing of debt, which is a worrying indicator of vice-chancellors' and other senior managers' preferences for legacy buildings over the sustainable provision of education.

We also address respondents' reports of the more personal experiences of redundancy processes, including the health impacts, the perceived effects on students, and lessons learned from mitigation and resistance attempts. Emerging or worsening mental health problems, trade union victimisation, the undermining of academic freedom, increased casualisation, increased workloads, lower morale and less collegiality are all pervasive in the survey responses.

Individuals facing redundancy likely disclose their often painful emotional responses with family and friends and with caseworkers, who are (hopefully) able to provide support. However, their experiences are rarely shared with a wider audience. Reading their testimonies can be difficult, especially for those who have suffered similar processes or experienced other forms of violence in the workplace. Additionally, whether down to fear for their own position or other reasons, co-workers can look the other way when colleagues are forced from jobs (and, by extension, work-based communities). But we *should* read people's responses in full whenever possible; people should not be silenced, vanished, and erased from our

⁴ Existing research does explore some impacts of financialised higher education. For example, the roles of debt, so-called off-balance sheet financial activities, and covenants in enabling University of Leicester managers to make mass redundancies of 2021 is discussed in detail in Chapter 5 of *Shaping for Mediocrity: The Cancellation of Critical Thinking at Our Universities*, by Gibson Burrell, Ronald Hartz, David Harvie, Geoff Lightfoot and Simon Lilley (Zero Books, 2024). In the US, the Coalition Against Campus Debt recently published an account of its research and organising activities, *Lend and Rule: Fighting the Shadow Financialization of Public Universities* (Common Notions, 2024).

universities by way of redundancy. In particular, we urge university leaders, policy makers, commentators, trade union officials, and all university workers to pay attention to the stories that people share.

The remainder of the report is structured as follows. First, we explain the methodology, present summary information about respondents, and point to areas where further research is required. Second, we discuss findings in detail. Third, we conclude with some suggestions for next steps. We have also included two appendices, in which we have reproduced the survey itself, and responses to one of survey's open-form questions.

METHODOLOGY

Aims and scope

This report analyses and presents responses to a survey of current and former UCU members' experiences of redundancies and resistance in UK higher education.

The survey's aim was threefold. First, to uncover the scale of job losses in universities and better understand how job cuts are being, or have been, implemented by managers. Second, to ask respondents about their experiences of UCU in relation to redundancies.⁵ And third, to hear from people whose stories about, experiences of, and perspectives on redundancy processes are often effaced from discussions about working conditions in universities.

The report focuses on responses to questions about the scale and implementation of job cuts.

Eligibility to participate

The survey was open to anyone who had worked at a higher education institution (HEI) where employers had threatened or implemented a range of job-cutting measures in the past five years.

Survey respondents may have directly experienced, witnessed, or heard about activities within their current or former branch that not only included redundancies, but also what the survey termed 'redundancies by the back door', such as non-renewal of fixed-term contracts, hiring freezes, protected conversations, voluntary severance schemes, and fire and rehire.

The survey did not ask for participants' names, email addresses, or for other information that may have led to their being identified by either employers or colleagues. As such, we take it on trust that respondents are sharing honest accounts of their experiences.

While a wide range of views is represented across the sample, none of the responses provide obviously malicious data that would significantly undermine the robustness of the results.

Distribution

The survey was first shared in mid-August 2024 and remained open until the end of October 2024. It was shared primarily via social media (Facebook and X/Twitter) from personal and UCU branch accounts, and was circulated via various union-related organising groups on their mailing lists. The survey was mentioned in UCU's centrally administered weekly 'Friday email' from the end of September 2024.

Respondents

The survey received 349 responses, with respondents spanning 97 higher education institutions. Of the 97 HEIs represented in the sample, 15 are members of the Russell Group. A further 30 are pre-92 institutions, and 52 are post-92 universities.

Coverage across the 97-HEI sample was uneven. For example, at over 30 institutions represented in the survey, just one respondent completed the questionnaire (with some writing as individuals, and at least

⁵The survey also elicited respondents' views on strategies and tactics for challenging redundancies, and on UCU's legal support mechanisms. This data has not been published at the time of writing this report.

one representing their branch). Yet from one particular institution, there were 17 respondents. The median number of respondents from an HEI was seven.⁶

Roughly two-thirds of respondents (229) were personally at risk of redundancy or had been in the past five years. The remaining one-third (120) were not, or had not been, personally at risk.

Of the 229 respondents who had personally experienced redundancy risk (currently or in the past five years), a little over one-quarter (62) had a formal role in their UCU branch, as a departmental rep, committee member, caseworker, and/or officer. Three were current or former members of UCU's national executive committee (NEC). Just over a third (44) of the 120 respondents who had not personally experienced redundancy risk held a formal union role in their local branch.

Data analysis

The survey received multiple responses from members employed (or formerly employed) by some HEIs. In these cases, we gave all responses equal weight, even where the information about experiences within the HEI differed. For instance, if just one respondent out of several from a particular institution reported that the employer was or had been bullying staff into applying for voluntary severance or redundancy, we treated this response as valid. On the basis that employers encourage staff to keep disclosures about their workplace treatment confidential, it is reasonable to suppose that there would be differences between staff members' knowledge of others' experiences within the same HEI.

We also treated all estimates of redundancy figures as valid. Thus, for a few institutions, the estimated number of jobs at risk ranges from one to more than 200. Discrepancies in redundancy figures among members of staff at the same institution could have a range of underlying causes. Given that confusing communications from employers about the scope of institutional restructuring and redundancy programmes is one possibility, the issue is important to highlight.

Areas for further investigation

While the data are not conclusive, the fact that 27% of respondents (62 out of 229) who had experienced redundancy risk also held formal union roles warrants further research; many respondents linked the two factors in their open-box responses. UCU members urgently need to investigate whether playing a prominent role in workplace organising makes you more likely to be bullied, put at risk of redundancy, or suffer some other form of career detriment.

Furthermore, while respondents were not asked questions about their identity beyond their role in UCU, it's clear from the survey's open-box responses that many people believe protected characteristics and other forms of marginalisation, such as migrant status, contribute to redundancy risk. Further research would enable UCU to uncover any potential for employer discrimination against marginalised staff in redundancy or related processes.⁷

⁶ In 15 cases we do not know the respondent's employer, or former employer, either because the respondent declined to name them or because they used an ambiguous acronym.

⁷ Discrimination against people based on their 'age, disability, gender reassignment, marriage and civil partnership, race, religion or belief, sex, or sexual orientation' is illegal under the Equality Act 2010, see <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2010/15/contents>.

FINDINGS

Redundancies: scale and means

Respondents at 59 of the 97 represented institutions reported that managers had made, or are currently making, compulsory redundancies. According to respondents, a minimum of 1461 people recently have been or currently are being affected by compulsory redundancies at the 97 HEIs they represent, with the likely maximum in the region of 9,000 people affected.

Based on respondents' estimates, we calculate that the number of people affected by 'backdoor' redundancy (hiring freezes, non-renewal of fixed-term contracts, voluntary severance and redundancy, protected conversations, and fire and rehire) is between 2519 and over 11,000.

It's reasonable to assume that the 'true' figures lie somewhere between the lower and upper bounds, suggesting that within the 97 represented HEIs around 5,200 university workers are affected by compulsory redundancy, and a further 6,700 by backdoor redundancies.

The respondents are drawn from just 97 of the UK's approximately 165 universities. The survey specifically invited responses from institutions where redundancies have been or are being implemented. Even if the survey had been open to a wider pool of participants, self-selection bias likely would have resulted in more responses from the same institutions. It's also the case that the survey's distribution was limited; it's probable that there have been redundancy programmes at other institutions not captured in the survey responses.

If survey findings were representative of job cuts across the whole sector, then extrapolating the data to all 165 UK HEIs, and taking the mid-point, approximately 8,900 staff are being or have been affected by compulsory redundancies, and 11,500 by backdoor redundancies. These figures could be much higher, with as many as 15,000 affected by compulsory and 20,000 by backdoor redundancies at the upper bounds. However, the figures could be lower if staff at the 68 HEIs unrepresented in the survey have more secure employment.⁸

According to Higher Education Statistics Agency (HESA) data, there were around 240,420 academic staff (both full time and part time) employed by higher education providers in 2022/23 and a further 62,690 academic staff employed on 'atypical' contracts.⁹ Thus – taking these HESA numbers as denominator and using our survey finding as numerator – it's likely that 6.7% of university staff (one in 15) are at risk; it's possible that as many as 11–12% (one in nine) are facing redundancy.

It's vital to reflect on the scale of what the survey calls 'redundancies by the backdoor', too, as these processes typically receive less public attention as they are conducted outside of the formal, legislated redundancy process, while nevertheless resulting in job losses. Respondents at 86 of the 97 HEIs represented in the survey reported that managers had imposed hiring freezes, often resulting in staff attrition. Respondents at 78 of the HEIs reported the non-renewal of at least some fixed-term contracts. Since around one third of academic staff are employed on a fixed-term contract – of duration typically between three months and four years – it's likely that this form of under-the-radar redundancy is threatening around 80,000 university workers.

⁸ Our findings are aligned with other UCU research, which suggests that 'over 10,000 staff [might] lose their jobs'. (<https://www.ucu.org.uk/article/13935/University-crisis-will-see-over-10000-staff-lose-their-jobs-fears-UCU>).

⁹ HESA doesn't record particularly reliable or consistent data on non-academic university employees. HESA's remit is also wider than just universities: in 2022/23, 260 higher education providers returned data to it. Our survey was specifically for university staff.

Equally common a means by which university managers are implementing job cuts are so-called voluntary redundancy and voluntary severance (so-called because many respondents note that the processes does not always feel like they enable voluntary decisions). One or both were reported by respondents at 82 of the survey's 97 represented institutions.

Less pervasive, but still common, were protected conversations. Respondents at almost half of the represented HEIs (45 out of 97) reported that university workers had left their employment as a result of the process. Protected conversations can be initiated by managers or employees and are held in secrecy (discussions are confidential unless the employee is being discriminated against, in which case a judge may allow the conversation to be discussed in an employment tribunal). The process typically results in the employee leaving their workplace quickly, without warning to colleagues, and having signed a non-disclosure agreement that prevents them from discussing their treatment. While some conversations are initiated by staff — protected conversations can be a convenient way for people to leave an unpleasant working environment on their own terms – we are concerned about reports of widespread use across the sector, especially given respondents' reports of managers targeting people with protected characteristics, and using bullying as a tactic in voluntary redundancy processes.

Furthermore, managers at one third of the HEIs (32 out of 97) mentioned in the survey were reported to have practised some form of fire and rehire – a practice that is unlawful. Fire and rehire was reported by 18% of the survey's respondents (62 out of 349).

Potentially unlawful practice?

According to survey respondents, management practices that could be judged unlawful in an employment tribunal are rife in redundancy processes across the sector. Respondents alleged the following forms of unethical and potentially unlawful behaviour by university managers:

- Misuse of protected conversations – at 29% of HEIs (28 out of 97). [Reported by 13% of respondents.]
- Failures to adhere to institutional policies governing redundancy processes – at 52% of HEIs (50 out of 97). [Reported by 37% of respondents.]
- Failures to follow legislation governing redundancy processes – at 45% of HEIs (44 out of 97). [Reported by 26% of respondents.]
- Bullying staff into applying for voluntary severance and/or voluntary redundancy – at 54% of HEIs (52 out of 97). [Reported by 33% of respondents.]
- Failure to adequately consult with those individuals at risk of redundancy – at 73% of HEIs (71 out of 97). [Reported by 59% of respondents.]
- Failure to adequately consult with relevant trade unions – at 69% of HEIs (67 out of 97). [Reported by 59% of respondents.]
- Failure to implement or accept suggested alternatives to redundancies – at 73% of HEIs (71 out of 97). [Reported by 63% of respondents.]

Redundancy causes

In almost all cases, respondents report that employers are citing financial pressures and/or declining student recruitment (particularly of what the sector calls 'international' students) for initiating job cuts. The responses additionally reveal two worrying and closely related trends. The first is university leaders'

pendant for campus expansion; the second is the way in which these leaders are taking on new debt (which frequently comes with stringent conditions, known as 'covenants', attached).

Thus, for instance, at one university, the main reason given for initiating job cuts was 'financial (loan covenants)'. At another, reasons given include 'estates upgrades', as well as finances, poor recruitment, and 'inefficiencies'. A respondent from yet another reported the following reason: 'financial constraints due to repayment of back covenant related to past building work that led to widespread restructuring with closure of several programmes'. At all of these HEIs, several hundred workers are currently (or have been) at risk of compulsory or backdoor redundancy.

One of the few exceptions to the 'financial' justification came from a respondent discussing a London-based Russell Group institution. Here, the respondent suggests, the ongoing restructuring (which reportedly might involve 1–10 compulsory and up to 200 backdoor redundancies), is for 'strategic reasons'. The respondent added that management were 'getting rid of people or teams they don't like when trying to make what they claim are improvements to services'.

The failure of leadership

Many respondents castigated the actions of university senior managers, describing their behaviour as 'abrupt', 'amateurish', 'intimidating', 'disrespectful', and 'cruel'.

According to respondents, managers at numerous HEIs are not properly setting up or consulting with relevant parties on redundancy processes. Among respondents facing redundancy, a lack of communication and care from management, and confusion and uncertainty, are commonly cited aggravators of stress and ill health. Some respondents report that during redundancy processes they have experienced, witnessed, or heard about managers using the following practices: pressuring employees to take voluntary severance, targeting people with protected characteristics or extended sick-leave records, threatening holders of Skilled Worker Visas, and targeting staff aged 50 and over.

For example:

'There was no real sense of transparency and I did not have confidence that it had been handled correctly.'

'We were called to a meeting a month before Xmas and told they needed to reduce us in number and we were at risk of redundancy [...] We had to spend the Xmas break applying for our own jobs.'

'Bottom line, I was the most expensive person in his school and he [the head of school] had savings to make.'

'Communication from the university leadership is poor, confusing, incorrect and disrespectful. The redundancy process is carried out without any care for the impact on the employees.'

'My departments were very, very good at what they did, and quite clearly, none of that is valued by our employer.'

Managerial bullying was a frequent theme that emerged from respondents' accounts of their experiences. One respondent suggested, for instance, that 'the university', [i.e. senior university managers] 'only wanted people to work there who couldn't leave (lived locally, caring responsibilities, lack of confidence, etc.) so they could be controlled and bullied and wouldn't leave'. Other respondents said:

'University management has a list of people who are harassed until they leave. They succeeded in a number of cases; in one case, a colleague was hospitalised after a prolonged bullying campaign; a few colleagues are still standing out of sheer stubbornness.'

'The tone from some senior management was quite intimidating and threatening.'

'Sickening to see university advertising for social justice. Corruption within HE is rampant. Look at who is being protected and why.'

Some respondents singled out the actions of Human Resources staff for their behaviour. For instance, one respondent shared that they were 'lied to' before being told a few weeks later that their role and team 'would no longer exist'.

'My treatment by my line manager lacked the basic duty of care practices that any manager would ideally show a colleague being made redundant. HR did not reach out to me once or support me adequately in formal meetings, [but] just defended the executive.'

'It is a war of attrition and the insane levels of aloofness from HR (solely supporting management) have prompted more than one member to observe "I think they hope I die".'

It's worth noting here that the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD), the professional association for human resource management professionals, has a strict Code of Conduct and Ethics.¹⁰ This Code reminds CIPD members that they have obligations not only to an organisation's senior managers, but also to its *employees*; it also warns members against 'bully[ing], harass[ing], abus[ing], victimis[ing], or conduct[ing] offensive behaviour in the work environment', and requires them to 'speak up about issues and concerns in the workplace'.

University leaders frequently narrate their restructuring and redundancy processes as one-off affairs, as an exercise that, 'painful' as it might be, will set the institution on a more stable trajectory. This, alas, is rarely the experience of those who work in higher education. The following response evokes this experience:

'Working here feels like getting knocked down by a disaster, pulling ourselves up again, just to be knocked over again. We've had four different organisational structures in the last nine years, each one ostensibly to make us more efficient, but each one in reality reducing the workforce and disrupting whatever workflows had started to grow back. Higher education is a team effort. How can a team grow [...] if it is torn apart every two years?'

Another respondent, referring to the 'shame' that many employees feel on being made redundant, reflected this back onto university leaders, whom they charge with 'academic vandalism':

'This is not our shame and we have done nothing to warrant redundancy. It is the shame of years of mismanagement, of turning universities into (poorly performing) businesses, and of politically motivated divestment from widening participation, and from the arts and humanities. [...] I feel devastated by the academic vandalism taking place at my university.'

Finally, the following extended comment provides a telling insight into the nature of many respondents' experiences of, and feelings about, contemporary university leadership:

'The process which is not over yet has been abysmally, malevolently mismanaged from the start. Numbers were faked and changed, procedures invented and changed, individuals and groups singled out and targeted, bullying via deadlines, admin and invented processes went on for months. No care or support to speak of and a deliberate lack of information and transparency to date. Staff made to feel indirectly, but also directly, a burden, a bunch of lazy shirkers, entitled losers and incompetent academics and teachers by SMT and HR managers who ensured minimum standards were employed and did not shy away from bullying those ill, disabled, with protected characteristics or experiencing

¹⁰ CIPD, *Code of Conduct and Ethics*, 2023, <https://www.cipd.org/globalassets/media/comms/code-of-conduct/2023-cipd-code-of-conduct-and-ethics.pdf>

trauma. Not a single manager has been showing their face on campus throughout [...] Staff who left were let go without acknowledgement of years of service and heads of department and other managerial academics were made accomplices throughout. It felt, as a colleague said, "like watching the birth of fascism", as colleagues singled out for redundancy were isolated deliberately.'

Impacts on workers

The effects of university managers' actions on workers' health, workloads, morale, security, ability to be critical of management tactics, and capacity to organise are predictable, yet nonetheless upsetting to read. Those who responded to the survey report the following:

- Emerging anxiety, stress, depression or other health problems – at 86% of HEIs (83 out of 97). [Reported by 90% of respondents.]
- Worsening of existing mental health or other health problems – at 85% of HEIs (82 out of 97). [Reported by 76% of respondents.]
- Trade union victimisation – at 45% of HEIs (44 out of 97). [Reported by 21% of respondents.]
- Undermining of academic freedom – at 61% of HEIs (59 out of 97). [Reported by 36% of respondents.]
- Targeting of people with protected characteristics – at 40% of HEIs (39 out of 97) . [Reported by 23% of respondents.];
- Targeting of people openly critical of management or institutional strategy – at 64% of HEIs (62 out of 97). [Reported by 36% of respondents.]
- Increased use of casualised contracts following redundancies – at 53% of HEIs (51 out of 97). [Reported by 39% of respondents.]
- Increased workloads of remaining staff when colleagues are made redundant redundancies – at 85% of HEIs (82 out of 97). [Reported by 87% of respondents.]
- Deterioration of working conditions, including collegiality and morale – at 86% of HEIs (84 out of 97). [Reported by 91% of respondents.]

Personal testimonies only compound the force of the raw numbers. Respondents shared often harrowing accounts of their mental and/or physical health conditions, trauma, impacts on their personal lives and careers, impacts on their families and breakdown of personal relationships, and various forms of racism, misogyny (including related to menopause or maternity leave), homophobia, anti-migrant attitudes, ageism (with older workers targeted), and ableism.

Three examples follow:

'I feel like I had no option but to accept vol[untary] severance and this was due to homophobia from a student/s and bullying by a course director. [The institution] actually blamed me for the homophobia telling me I should not have spoken so much about LGBTQ issues even though I am an openly gay man teaching on a course concerning intersectionality. Meanwhile following a data access request I realised the [course director] had done nothing to stop the student leaving homophobic comments online and later sending homophobic emails to me.'

'As a BAME person, I've experienced institutional racism [...] I was unfairly dismissed [...] (the university made my position redundant and then employed somebody else for lower pay to do my job). I disputed all these issues with the university for two years and became so unwell as a result that I developed

severe anxiety and panic attacks. I eventually had a nervous breakdown and sought the help of a psychiatrist, who stated that I had a completely deregulated nervous system. The two-year battle with the university also ruined my relationship and my partner left me because I was constantly stressed, couldn't sleep, and had panic attacks, and he couldn't stand it.'

'I have heard about colleagues on visas that they feel especially threatened because depending on their visa arrangements, they may have very limited time to leave the country (including taking kids out from school, arranging relocation etc.) if they are being made redundant.'

Many respondents mentioned the stress-inducing and demoralising effects of redundancy processes – both during the process itself and in the aftermath – with colleagues often pitted against one another.

Words used by respondents to describe their university workplace environments, their experiences, and associated emotional responses included: 'powerless', 'distressing', 'traumatising', 'devastating', 'hostile environment', 'dehumanising', 'silencing', 'undermining', 'bullying', 'brutal', 'toxic', 'barbaric', and 'soul-destroying'.

The following testimony is evocative of the wide-ranging and multiple impacts:

'Being placed at risk of redundancy and the mishandling of the process took a huge toll on my mental (and physical) health. [...] While there were (officially) no compulsory redundancies, I am sure that many colleagues felt "pushed out" and took voluntary redundancy because they did not feel safe. We lost over 200 colleagues. There has been no aftercare process and it seems I am expected to simply pick up where I left off with no acknowledgment of the trauma inflicted by the process and the impact this has had on my working and personal life. Workloads have increased and colleagues feel insecure. Senior management have refused to engage with union questions about their responsibility for poor financial management. The whole redundancy process was dehumanising, it has left me burnt-out and demoralised.'

Many respondents noted not only the psychological toll of being made redundant (e.g., a 'loss of self-confidence') but the way in which apparently individual psychological and/or emotional impacts have far wider and long-lasting repercussions, on the individual, their capacities, and on those around them.

'The worst thing that has happened to me in my career.'

'Made me to feel useless and that I failed. Very bad impact to my family's life.'

'Plunged my family into poverty. Made me ill with stress. Depressing that while we were made unemployed they were simultaneously bragging about building brand new buildings.'

'I sat in the "consultation" meeting sobbing. No-one at the front (those consulting with us) checked on my welfare. I found colleagues distraught in their offices – again, no one had checked in on them. I haven't been able to sleep properly for the last month, my concentration has been destroyed, I haven't been able to plan or commit to anything within work or indeed outside of work. I should have been signed off work with stress but was too scared to be 'outside' of the process. After 17 years in my role I feel utterly betrayed.'

'One colleague was off for six weeks and had to take antidepressants, another was off sick with stress-related high blood pressure. I was off for two months with chest pains and work-related stress. The impact of this experience is still playing out and I am finding it very difficult to even think about looking for another job.'

Also remarkable are the acts of historical erasure by which respondents report that managers have made certain groups of current and former employees invisible or devalued. One professional services member of staff wrote, for instance:

'There's been less visibility than for academic redundancies; it makes me feel undervalued.'

Other responses on this theme included:

'It makes it clear that you are not valued and implies your work – ultimately – doesn't matter if you're a perceived burden on the financial bottom line. Colleagues who took VS just disappeared, their years of service and the knowledge they accumulated just written off as if it never existed.'

'I'd worked there a decade, done everything I've ever been asked and it just didn't seem to matter.'

Finally, it's worth emphasising that redundancy processes affect *all* staff, including those that remain in employment. Survey respondents report that the impacts on remaining staff include: the undermining of academic freedom, the degradation of trust in universities as institutions, increased workloads, diminished staff morale, and the creation of a 'climate of fear'.

'Have kept a job but feel unsettled and anxious and also feel that if I speak out too much I will be targeted in the next round. Feel negatively affected by low morale and climate of fear all around me.'

'Our university has given a pompous name to the process of reshaping the work and workload of who is left which – de facto – amounts to covering holes, more workload, less freedom on how to do the work (less academic freedom) and, in the end, less services for staff and students.'

'There is [...] an atmosphere of fear and intimidation for any who do not toe the line. I love this university but despise its hateful, greedy and mostly incompetent leadership. If I had an option to leave, I would take it now.'

'I am a senior professor with 30+ years' experience. The entire financial cuts process has entirely ruined my relationship with my employer and indeed even with the sector. I have zero respect for senior/middle management in my own institution who either caused or operationalised the situation. Fuck them. Join your union!'

Impacts on students

University redundancy processes not only affect only university workers (and their [chosen] families, support networks, and wider communities), but also students. The impacts on students are wide-ranging and, say respondents, entirely negative.

'The key thing is to try to make it clear to the public, and prospective students and families as well as employers etc, that this damage to HE impacts us all in terms of standard of education and training, career prospects and future wellbeing and prosperity.'

'We keep telling management that we as academics are overworked and abused in some respects but not consulted on matters in which we are experts, such as student recruitment. The resource that is our experience and expertise is too often side-stepped and wasted.'

'Entire teaching – apart from what I contribute – is basically training for a job. It is completely soul destroying that this is what university in the UK in 2024 is like.'

'I've moved out of HE altogether as I wanted to work for a new university and help disadvantaged students, but I don't think this will be an option due to the lack of funds for the next few years.'

'We are anxious and stressed. We are taking on more and more workload to try to reduce the risk, but at the detriment to our own quality of teaching, mental health and student learning and the student experience.'

'Colleagues working in the British system are able and willing to provide excellent education but are being hindered by uncertainty and excessive workloads. Decisions in the education sector are made based on what money is available, not on the intended quality. Hence the quality suffers. I stress – this is not due to colleagues' inability or unwillingness, but purely due to what is humanly possible to deliver.'

'The British education system is cheating the British youth.'

'Where is the debate and discussion and students who come for love of the subject and passion for learning? All of this has been reduced to "customers" paying ~£9k a year to be spoon-fed job training. What is the point??? Honestly if I could get out [...] I would.'

It's worth noting that the survey did not explicitly ask respondents about the impacts of job cuts on students. That so many people chose to address how students are affected by management decision-making is testament to the care that so many staff continue to demonstrate for students, even amid threats to their own livelihood. University staff working conditions are student learning conditions – which, after all, are everyone's living conditions.

NEXT STEPS

Whatever the cause and actuality of 'crisis' in any given institution, university senior managers and politicians in successive governments have chosen to sacrifice staff (and students) rather than administer changes that would stabilise the sector. While we do not know the scope of their suggested alternatives, three-quarters of survey respondents reported that employers have not implemented or accepted worker-led plans that could avoid job cuts. Since more than two-thirds of survey respondents report that managers have failed to adequately consult with relevant trade unions about redundancies, the rhetoric deployed by many management teams that they are making 'difficult decisions' rings hollow.

These same senior management teams have been complicit in the marketisation of universities and continue to be complicit (even if, in some cases, their embrace has been reluctant). Senior managers have *chosen* to divert limited resources into new buildings, rebranding exercises, and gaming the various performance metrics (REF, TEF, NSS, etc.). They are the magicians behind the curtains who divert attention to the university's façade, while simultaneously ripping apart the social fabric of research and teaching communities. The result is the university as *trompe l'oeil*.

Past decisions by university managers to take on debt (on behalf of 'their' institutions and its staff and students) will typically have repercussions over many decades, with repayments liable for perhaps 50 years. Debt is a disciplinary device that binds the future to the present and the past. As well as interest payments, creditors may also impose certain conditions, such as stipulating minimum financial returns on student accommodation (likely pushing up rents) and a maximum ratio of wage costs to income (likely depressing employment and/or salaries). These conditions are known as *covenants*. Thus, in the absence of a strong debtors' movement (which we suggest is an urgent necessity), universities – that is, workers and students – will be constrained by debts' strictures for some time into the future.

It's imperative, therefore, that more research is conducted into university finances so that UCU members and union staff are better positioned to fight for the university's potential, rather than defend the status quo. University workers and students must be able to hold senior managers accountable for decision making.

We also propose that more research should be conducted into unethical and potentially unlawful practices in redundancy processes, and that records should be kept detailing who is being targeted (for example, those with protected characteristics) and which subject areas are affected. We encourage union organisers (especially elected UCU officers and representatives) to undertake such research with urgency. Anonymous UCU member 'leaver surveys' at the point of exiting an employment would be one means of collecting data. Without this or similar research, the catastrophic changes wrought within the sector cannot be properly understood or resisted.

Furthermore, we argue that it's of critical importance that we all understand job cuts, course closures, student fee increases, and disinvestment from research not only as financially motivated, but also ideological. Many respondents pointed to the loss of their academic freedom (especially in relation to curriculum design) in their open-box responses, with at least one person recognising the redundancy process at their institution as a weapon of 'fascism'.

Under an authoritarian and wilfully passive government, it is significant that the management class feels free to target university workers who are marginalised by race, gender, sexuality, disability, migrant status, and trade union membership. Our universities – which ideally can provide spaces of creative and critical inquiry, community, and collaboration – are being hollowed out by small yet powerful groups of people. University leaders grow financially richer by making our communities poorer (that is, more homogenous). When they have finished wreaking havoc at one institution, many senior managers simply move on to the next. Meanwhile, the workers with knowledges and skillsets that enable them to challenge institutional powers find themselves, as survey respondents repeatedly evidence, 'at risk' of removal from their communities. What began as a sector-wide programme of mass casualisation, which constrains workers'

resistance to marketisation and maintenance of academic freedom, continues to gain momentum as managers cut ever-greater numbers of once comparatively 'safe' staff (those on open-ended contracts) from payrolls.

Many students, already burdened with debt, become more vulnerable as the scale of job cuts worsens. They face declining quality of education owing to the loss of staff knowledge and skills, overworked and demoralised staff, and the creeping use of generative AI in curriculum design and support services. Moreover, they are let down by the dogma of a labour-oriented education in which managers would have staff prioritise employability and external partnerships over all else. Senior management responses to students (and workers) protesting against universities' financial complicity in the Israeli state's genocide of Palestinians are indicative of hostile 'learning' environments on many campuses.¹¹

In the UK higher education sector, then, workers and students face increasingly dictatorial managerial demands to comply with state and ultimately corporate interests. Financial crises are ideological crises inextricably bound up in coloniality and racism, patriarchy, classism, queer- and transphobia, and ableism, all of which underpin neoliberal capitalism, and the current iterations of fascism that so many people are experiencing.

It is not possible for this report to recommend solutions to such deep-rooted violence in our universities. We need multifaceted, imaginative, and surprising strategies that must come from grassroots organising and critical analysis of the material conditions shaping higher education.¹²

Nevertheless, we do urge, as an important next step, that all readers of this report – that is, you – pay attention to the context in which financial crises are being created, who is making and benefitting from them, who is resisting them, and who is being harmed.

We also encourage you honour the experiences of those who shared their stories via the survey discussed in this report. If you work in a university or college or lead a professional body, make space for people to continue participating (should they wish to) in research, teaching, and learning wherever possible. Make your subject association accessible to them. Keep citing them, saying their names, and reminding those who seek to erase them that these former colleagues existed and mattered to you.

And finally, amid the rise of authoritarian and fascistic governments globally, take collective action – whatever your role, whoever your employer – to resist the top-down, ideologically driven destruction of education's radical potential to help transform our worlds for the better.

¹¹ Aaron Walawalkar and Harriet Clugston, "Uncovered: The 'Worsening Crackdown' on Pro-Palestine Activism at UK Universities," *Liberty Investigates*, February 22, 2025, <https://tinyurl.com/4cye77hy>.

¹² As authors, we have used the term 'higher' education as it is widely recognised by the various groups we hope will engage with this report. However, in reimagining education, we would dispense with notions of hierarchy and superiority.

APPENDICES

Notes

The survey asked an open-box question about personal experiences of redundancy processes.

All relevant responses (i.e., those that respond to the specific question asked) are included below. It is imperative that we challenge the silencing of people whose jobs have been put at risk, and that we ensure the experiences of those forced out of the sector are not erased.

Answers stating 'not applicable' or 'none' have been removed. Some spellings, abbreviations and grammar have been standardised for readability. Comments naming employers or giving other identifying information have been redacted. No substantive changes have been made.

Content notes

Please note that some of the answers given may be distressing to read. Respondents refer to: mental health conditions; physical health; trauma; negative impacts on personal lives and careers; negative impacts on family members; gender-based violence; and various forms of racism, misogyny, homophobia, anti-migrant attitudes, ageism, elitism, and ableism.

The report's authors do not necessarily agree with respondents' views.

Survey text and questions

The survey was produced using Google forms and was open to responses between August and October 2024.

Introductory text

Across the sector there are mass job losses taking place. At some institutions facing compulsory redundancies - and at others where CR is apparently not a concern – we're also experiencing protected conversations [1], voluntary redundancy, and hire freezes leading to mass redundancies by the back door [2]. Fixed-term contracts are not being renewed, and people are reporting bullying and/or pressure to take a 'voluntary' package. These tactics enable employers to claim they've avoided inflicting compulsory redundancies at our universities. The impacts of redundancies on everyone affected is enormous.

If you, your branch, or your former branch have been experiencing redundancy processes of any kind, please share what information you can via this form, which is owned by [UCU branch]. We welcome responses from former members who are no longer working in the sector owing to a redundancy process. There are 12 required questions, mostly multiple-choice, which will take around 5-10mins to complete. There are 6 optional questions that will take 5-30mins depending on the amount of detail that you want to give.

We plan to share findings with members, organise follow-up actions (including via branch delegate meetings and Higher Education Committee), and use the data to lobby national UCU and elsewhere for additional support. Your answers will help us expose often hidden and always harmful practices, and hold employers to account. We hope the responses you share will enable more branch cooperation and creative strategies in our shared struggle to make radically different universities. The survey will be open until October 14, 2024. Please share it widely.

[1] For more information about protected conversations, see <https://www.ibblaw.co.uk/insights/blog/5-things-you-need-know-about-protected-conversations>.

[2] You can find out more about your rights during redundancy processes at <https://www.acas.org.uk/your-rights-during-redundancy/how-your-employer-must-consult-you>. There is UCU guidance available at https://my.ucu.org.uk/app/answers/detail/a_id/29/kw/redundancy.

Q1

What is or was your branch? (Please enter your former branch and 'disaffiliated' if you are no longer working in the sector owing to a redundancy process. You don't need to use 'The', 'University of' or 'University').

Q2

How are or were you involved in UCU? Tick all that apply.

- Member
- Department rep
- Caseworker
- Branch committee member
- Branch committee officer
- Current or former NEC member

Q3

Are you, or have you been in the last five years, at risk of redundancy?

- Yes
- No

Q4

Have you or members in your (former) branch experienced any of the following in the past five years? Tick all that apply.

- Hiring freezes
- Non-renewal of fixed-term contracts
- Protected conversations
- Fire and rehire
- Voluntary severance
- Voluntary redundancies
- Compulsory redundancies

Q5

Are these processes historic or ongoing?

- Historic
- Ongoing
- Some processes are historic, others are ongoing

Q6

What is the main reason your current or former employer gave for initiating job cuts?

Q7

Do you think there are alternative solutions available to the employer other than redundancies?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

Q8

How many colleagues do you estimate have been or are being affected by compulsory redundancies in your branch?

- 1-10
- 11-50
- 51-100
- 101-200
- 200+

Q9

How many colleagues do you estimate have been or are being made redundant by the back-door (i.e. through protected conversations, hire freezes, VS, or VR)?

- 1-10
- 11-50
- 51-100
- 101-200
- 200+

Q10

Have you been affected by, observed, or been informed about any of the following in a redundancy process? Tick all that apply.

- Misuse of protected conversations
- Employer failures to adhere to institutional policies governing redundancy processes
- Employer failures to follow legislation governing redundancy processes
- Fire and rehire
- Bullying of staff into applying for voluntary severance
- Bullying of staff into applying for voluntary redundancy
- Failure of employers to adequately consult with those at risk
- Failure of employers to adequately consult with relevant unions
- Refusal of employers to implement/accept suggested alternatives to redundancies
- None of the above

Q11

Have you experienced, observed, or been informed about the following impacts on people affected by redundancy processes in your (former) branch? Tick all that apply.

- Emerging anxiety, stress, depression or other health problems
- Worsening of existing mental health or other health problems
- Trade union victimisation
- Undermining of academic freedom
- Targeting of people with protected characteristics
- Targeting of people openly critical of management or institutional strategy
- Increased use of casualised contracts following redundancies
- Increased workloads of remaining staff when colleagues are made redundant
- Deterioration of working conditions, including collegiality and morale
- None of the above

Q12

What action did your (former) branch take, or what action is it taking, to fight redundancies? Tick all that apply.

- Negotiating with employers and presenting alternative strategies
- Balloting for industrial action
- Action short of a strike (including a marking and assessment boycott)
- Strikes
- Academic boycott/greylisting
- Other campaigning tactics, e.g. public engagement
- Applied to UCU head office to ballot but refused permission
- Not sure
- None of the above

Q13

Has your branch successfully fought off compulsory redundancies?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

Q14

If your branch was successful in fighting compulsory redundancies, what do you think was key to your success? If you lost, is there anything you learned from the process that you'd like to share with other branches?

Q15

Have you tried to access UCU legal support in relation to a redundancy process?

– Yes

– No

Q16

If you have tried to access UCU legal support, what was your experience of the process?

Q17

Redundancy processes are not only harmful to those affected, but also silencing. We'd like to publish anonymous accounts from anyone who can share how a redundancy process affected them (we won't share branch details with any testimonies). If you're willing and able to do so, please share your thoughts and feelings about the experience below. We recommend having a good support network in place for aftercare.

Q18

Finally, are there any campaign strategies, tactics, or resources that you think would help at either branch or sector level to fight redundancies? Do you have any other comments you'd like to share?

Thanks for your time and energy in completing the survey.

Open-box responses

'Redundancy processes are not only harmful to those affected, but also silencing. We'd like to publish anonymous accounts from anyone who can share how a redundancy process affected them (we won't share branch details with any testimonies). If you're willing and able to do so, please share your thoughts and feelings about the experience below. We recommend having a good support network in place for aftercare.'

My department (in academic support) is currently going through a redundancy process. This began as solicitation for VR under threat of CR. The window for applications was 3 weeks, and this was followed by swift announcement of CR and notification of colleagues. The management is engaging with union reps as legally required, but there are some issues (for example, beginning collecting CR evidence before process and criteria have been agreed with unions and colleagues under the argument that 'sufficient time is needed'; pressuring some colleagues to provide feedback on work to be considered in CR with turnaround times as little as one day). Colleagues in the department report that workload remains high and that the redundancy process is making this issue worse, and that morale is low and exhaustion/stress high even for those whose jobs are not at risk.

There is a lot of bad feeling over the fact that poor financial planning by management (i.e., basing future projections on an unusual spike in applications due to Covid) has resulted in the 'need' for job losses. It has also placed stress on everyone affected as we have essentially been pitted against each other, which is tremendously bad for morale.

All who applied in my department were given the unspoken impression that they would be forced out due to their sickness records, this most heavily impacted staff with mental health issues.

I was threatened with VR in 2022 when my entire subject team was disbanded and the course discontinued. I was put into a 'pool' in which 5 FTE staff would be reduced to 3 FTE through a 'selection to stay' contest. As it happened, enough of the other staff took VR that I was kept on automatically. It was honestly the worst thing that has happened to me in my career. I was shoehorned into another subject team, which had literally no correlation with either my research or my teaching, but which the university management decided were similar enough to be put together, and then had to waste months of my career trying to fit together a coherent new curriculum which incorporated me and the rump of the other team I was forced to join. I had to take on all of the supervision or examining of the postgraduate research community which my previous subject team had built up, but who had been dumped by the restructure, with apparently not a second thought given to them by the management who made this decision. I also had to integrate two cohorts of undergraduate students who were being taught out into the new subject area and deal with the deep dissatisfaction and anger amongst them at what had happened. It was literally the worst academic year of my life - I basically became research inactive as I had no research mentorship or even anyone in the university who I could even talk to about my ideas for funding or publications. I had been awarded a sabbatical of 6 months which was then cancelled because I was needed to do the teaching of my redundant colleagues. At the end of that first year in the new team, I left to join a new team (which is little better, but it is slightly better - anything would be). This new team is made up of people who have transferred into the university from industry so none of them has the first idea about research and the entire teaching - apart from what I contribute - is basically training for a job. It is completely soul-destroying that this is what university in the UK in 2024 is like. Where is the debate and discussion and students who come for love of the subject and passion for learning? All of this has been reduced to 'customers' paying ~£9k a year to be spoon-fed job training. What is the point??? Honestly, if I could get out and switch career, I would.

The atmosphere made the whole university so difficult to work for that I just handed my notice in and left. I went to work for the university originally because it was good to work for. But the culture changed and seemed like the university only wanted people to work there who couldn't leave (lived locally, caring responsibilities, lack of confidence, etc.) so they could be controlled and bullied and wouldn't leave.

Anyone else who was good at their job and could move elsewhere did. I wasn't at risk of redundancy, but seeing how academic colleagues and others were treated and how I was treated was traumatic. I wanted to help the students who were from disadvantaged backgrounds, but there were so few staff that I felt there weren't the basics weren't in place and I felt I couldn't help them. The management style changed and I felt like you couldn't actually say what you thought anymore, you had to go along with whatever your manager said even if it wasn't true. And I saw colleagues turn on each other across the whole university. I have never felt like this at work before and had to leave. Lots of other staff just left because without other jobs to go for because they couldn't work there anymore. I've moved out of HE altogether as I wanted to work for a new university and help disadvantaged students, but I don't think this will be an option due to the lack of funds for the next few years.

Since I became affected by a redundancy consultation, I experienced three separate bouts of physical illness in just over a month. I had to be signed off work for several weeks due to the stress causing these illnesses. The stress I experienced was due to a combination of factors, including the impact on myself as Skilled Worker Visa holder, the impact on my line report and the general low mood amongst colleagues.

Working with the threat of redundancy hanging over your head is tough. It makes it clear that you are not valued and implies your work – ultimately – doesn't matter if you're a perceived burden on the financial bottom line. Colleagues who took VS just disappeared, their years of service and the knowledge they accumulated just written off as if it never existed.

I was not at risk of redundancy, but my friends in another department were. There were tears. It was a major scare. Some people took VS. The scoring for compulsory redundancies, based on what I heard, seemed disingenuous. If the issue is too many staff per student, then those who teach a lot should not be in the redundancy pool. VC/SLT communications were vague, which made people feel worse. UCU proposed a voluntary pay cut among SLT, to no avail. The University hired a new member to join the SLT for a completely new role after the redundancy talks began. This was a farce. Management is ever growing and all-consuming, while teaching and admin staff numbers are shrinking.

University management has a list of people who are harassed until they leave. They succeeded in a number of cases; in one case, a colleague was hospitalised after a prolonged bullying campaign; a few colleagues are still standing out of sheer stubbornness. This was so painful. I continue to think that the process used was borderline illegal. It was so incompetently run that I still struggle to believe that somehow, a process that poor, could have cost me my job. Management dismissed our concerns, refused to provide key information, twisted their own words and ours to justify decisions they had clearly already made. I don't know how I am going to trust them again. I was left feeling very powerless as there seems to be no way to make management reckon with their failures or force accountability within the process - the only possible redress is through a tribunal. The timeline was brutal and I lost a month of much needed summer break (for research and rest, as we cannot take time through term) to reapply for my own job. In the wake of it, those of us who remain are left to pick up the pieces and work out how we are to deliver our programme next year. I remain just so sad, as until this happened, despite the overwork, I actually loved my job. My departments were very, very good at what they did, and quite clearly, none of that is valued by our employer.

I am a senior professor with 30+ years' experience. The entire financial cuts process has entirely ruined my relationship with my employer and indeed even with the sector. I have zero respect for senior/middle management in my own institution who either caused or operationalised the situation. Fuck them. Join your union!

I can't believe the whole thing was handled so poorly. The number of errors that were made became darkly comical as well as predictable. The union also made some major screwups (how was research not originally included in the application process?). The whole thing was a big mess and smacked of a pilot run for a bigger round of redundancies in the not too distant future.

My experience was distressing. As a mum of two, being at risk at a time when there are no jobs to go to was a horrible place to be. I was placed in a pool of three people; two of us had to go. Significant research buy out from a prestigious funder made no difference to the selection criteria despite arguments that the pool was created for money saving measures. This created a situation where VR was really CR for 2 people. Emotional support was offered as a formality as part of the consultation process but management didn't check in on any of us for the three months the process continued. The day before I had to reapply for my job, I was told the situation was resolved. Two of us remain in post and one has taken leave. We've had no explanation of why this happened or what changed for us to stay. There are now teaching gaps and staff are being asked to volunteer to cover teaching and fixed-term staff are plugging gaps. Morale is low and excellent staff feel under-valued. We remain in limbo about whether our discipline has a future. We need our managers and leaders to lobby for change on behalf of the sector. We need government to rectify the policies that have led to this damaging and precarious situation for staff and students. Staff who deliver education are being picked off and the threat remains over us. It's stressful and highly uncertain as we will probably have to reapply for jobs we are already doing not knowing if we will get them.

Contesting my own redundancy and that of 145 other colleagues, over a 7-month period, was one of most intense political experiences of my life. I experienced pretty much every emotion: optimism, rage, joy, distress, despair. The care and solidarity I received from some friends, comrades and (former) colleagues was incredibly moving. The carelessness with which I — and my comrades and (former) colleagues — were treated by bosses, too many other former colleagues and too many leading figures in our union was distressing and traumatising. Following my eventual dismissal I suffered from poor health (heightened anxiety and exhaustion) for at least two years. It's only three years later, and following the partially successful outcome of an employment tribunal (which was problematic and distressing in itself), that I feel I am mostly restored to fullish health.

Devastating - I'd worked there a decade, done everything I've ever been asked and it just didn't seem to matter. My team was dismantled outside of/ahead of the formal process and consultation with no business reason for doing so - it served the interest of the executive member who took over my staff. Another of my team members was put into another team but given literally no new work to do - not one task - for several months - until their role was then made redundant in the next wave of restructure. I was lied to about my team having an opportunity to develop a new plan - a few weeks later I was told my role and team would no longer exist. My treatment by my line manager lacked the basic duty of care practices that any manager would ideally show a colleague being made redundant. HR did not reach out to me once or support me adequately in formal meetings, just defended the executive. In all of this I had no issue with the fact that redundancies were necessary but being treated humanely and respectfully would have made a big difference.

Absolute panic that you will be next despite the quality of one's work and commitment to teaching and research! Makes you feel on edge and like you cannot make any long term plans even if one has a sought-after permanent contract.

My university has made it clear that managers have grouped academics into two distinct categories: those who generate income (teaching-focused academics, research-focused academics with external grants, any academic with industrial links) and those who do not (generally research-focused academics who do not currently hold any external grants). This generates a strong sense of whether one is 'safe', or not. This in turn has polarised our department, with the 'unsafe' people either suddenly removing themselves from all team activity (so as not to raise their head above the parapet), or suddenly becoming hyper-engaged in everything (in order to look busy). This creates an unusual dynamic we do not know how to deal with, contributing to tensions in the workplace, low morale, and deterioration of collegiality. Ironically, this alteration in behaviour of the 'unsafe' colleagues is actually wasting money, as many of them are creating vanity projects to generate impact and tick boxes on management paperwork to secure their jobs. As such, the hostile environment created by threats of redundancy is actually losing the university money, not saving it as managers intend.

The process which is not over yet has been abysmally, malevolently mismanaged from the start. Numbers were faked and changed, procedures invented and changed, individuals and groups singled out and targeted, bullying via deadlines, admin and invented processes went on for months. No care or support to speak of and a deliberate lack of information and transparency to date. Staff made to seem indirectly, but also directly, a burden, a bunch of lazy shirkers, entitled losers and incompetent academics and teachers by SMT and HR managers who ensured minimum standards were employed and did not shy away from bullying those ill, disabled, with protected characteristics or experiencing trauma. Not a single manager has been showing their face on campus throughout. Complaints procedures were sent and grievances redefined unilaterally into 'complaints'. Staff who left were let go without acknowledgement of years of service and HoDs and other managerial academics were made accomplices throughout. It felt, as a colleague said, 'like watching the birth of fascism', as colleagues singled out for redundancy were isolated deliberately and their line managers as well colleagues [authors' note: The wordcount seems to have been reached and cut off the last few words of the response].

Plunged my family into poverty. Made me ill with stress. Depressing that while we were made unemployed they were simultaneously bragging about building brand new buildings with "designer" toilets. Also disgusting that everyone on SLT remained in post with hyper inflated salaries while up to 50 per cent of those below them are simply culled. SLT not held unaccountable for their poor strategy and lack of decision making. SLT mainly seem to work from home, showing up occasionally with swinging lanyard round neck and key jangling. Rude, disrespectful bullies. Not clear what they actually usefully do or how they add value and why they were chosen for that position. Sickening to see university advertising for social justice. Corruption within HE is rampant. Look at who is being protected and why. Honestly think sector needs total review. It is unethical, fake, exploitative and full of incompetency. The fees are lining someone's pocket but it isn't the students' futures.

The process was cursory, and the communication style abrupt, favouring the management, for example it was repeated to me that my application would be considered at their discretion and they were under no obligation to accept my application. The process guidance was being developed as the scheme was launched and I found out after I had applied that I should have had a discussion with my line manager. Such things were not in place when I applied. Once my application was in, I heard nothing and requests for updates were ignored. Five weeks passed before the VS was confirmed but again, no details were forthcoming as to when and how the severance would be paid or why the university was refusing to let me retire early. Once granted VS, I had no contact or support from my manager and there were no transition arrangements put in place for students affected by my going. We were told to take all leave owing and to deliver all uni equipment by the 31st July. I was cut off from university communications on the 1st August.

I saw the direction that UKHE was heading in and accepted an academic job in the USA just one year into my employment at [name of university].

I was put "at risk of redundancy" in March 2024, but then told my job was being moved to another area of the University group, and I'd have priority in applying for it. I questioned why I would have to re-apply for my own job if it was my job, and I'd not be being made redundant if that was the case - it should be a TUPE. HR eventually agreed that I wouldn't apply for the job and I'd be just slotted in, but that I'd nevertheless be made redundant in my current role, and I'd get the statutory payout which was about ~£5k. I was told I'd be moving to another operational division, but the JD [job description] for the new role had a logo on it from a subsidiary of the University that I knew that team wasn't operationally aligned to, so I was confused. I kept asking questions and having meetings with HR and the PVC about how they were determining my pay as the new role was aligned to a different pay structure, and what would be the terms of my new employment contract. They couldn't tell me any firm answers, and I had no clarity from them on any aspect. They pressed on with the redundancy process, and I was invited to my individual "at-risk" meeting at the end of April, and was given my letter of redundancy with the payment details on it, saying my contract would end on July 31st, I'd be paid my redundancy pay and then I'd move onto my new contract on 1st August (which was my existing job but in another subsidiary, which they still wouldn't be clear on which one). The week before my employment was due to end in July, HR contacted me to say they

wouldn't pay my redundancy, because they'd now decided it wasn't a redundancy situation. They also told me I'd not be based in the team they'd originally proposed throughout the consultation process, but in another team, which was based operationally in yet another subsidiary, which would be a different legal employing entity again. I was angry that they'd changed tack from redundancy to TUPE so late and hadn't properly consulted me on the foreseen legal conditions of my new employer. Under TUPE regulations, it's "the transferor's duty to consult affected employees on the envisaged legal, economic, and social changes for the employees, subject to the transfer process." In my opinion it is a breach of an employer's duty of trust (by the transferor as the parent company and controlling party), if its employees are transferred without full advance provision for understanding the envisaged terms and conditions of the entity to which they'll be transferred. I have not been able to give informed consent to a proposed change, if Information was either withheld, changed, or actively concealed through the process. It's also a breach of duty to the union if they aren't giving sufficient information to the unions as staff representatives, such that they can advise their members appropriately. There was no advance provision of contract or sufficient pay information such that I was able to consider the social, economic and legal impact of my transfer. It was only after my start date in my new role on [date] that I was issued a contract, which is in fact with a completely different entity AGAIN, that was never mentioned during the process - and containing worse terms and conditions than my previous contract. I'd already started my job so I was now unable to consider the impact before starting.

Significant impact on retirement plans when employer not willing to offer an option for premature retirement for those over 55.

Inter-colleague tensions and anxiety are rife.

I wouldn't mind a fair and genuine redundancy process. However, I felt like the management wasn't trying to avoid redundancies (through re-training and redeployment, for instance); as if they got a gold star for every person they made redundant. The targeted pool was extremely arbitrary and felt like a personal vendetta. Every point raised during the consultation and appeal was met with a "fake news" attitude. Made me lose trust in the quality of managerial decisions. Felt like some life-changing decisions were made willy-nilly, based on very poor understanding of data.

Redundancy consultations were sprung upon the staff with little warning. Most staff were pressurised into taking voluntary severance or voluntary redundancy. The management simply ignored challenges to reverse the redundancies. There were two of us with the same role and we were told we would both need to apply for VR. My colleague was seconded to a higher position in the team that was making the redundancies. I was seconded to a higher role in a different team. Because our substantive posts no longer existed we were both told we'd be better off applying for VR. We both did. Mine was accepted but my colleague's was turned down as they wanted to keep her in the role she was seconded to and make her permanent in that role. This struck me as pretty underhand.

This is the 3rd cycle of redundancies at our university, so morale was low and stress high before the latest announcements of job cuts. As a Branch Officer involved in consultation and negotiation in two rounds of redundancy, I can see a deterioration in the quality of managers and HR's response to handling redundancies. There is a lack of preparation, and professionalism in consulting with TUs [trade unions], a lack of care in communicating with staff, this causes avoidable stress. Our university refused us the support of a regional official at formal consultation meetings concerning 150 redundancies, that is an indication of how amateurish management are at our uni. During consultation our questions and suggestions go unanswered, or the answers are mostly gibberish and contradictory. Few UCU members believe that our university will survive much longer, three-five years tops. Management failure, governance failure, political failure.

I was not approved for VR despite "applying", and then ended up signed off with stress for three months. More staff have since left, resulting in increased workloads to cover the required teaching.

Our university had a redundancy process about five years ago and is going through redundancies right now, again. In-between we had the Covid crisis. Working here feels like getting knocked down by a disaster, pulling ourselves up again, just to be knocked over again. We've had four different organisational structures in the last nine years, each one ostensibly to make us more efficient, but each one in reality reducing the workforce and disrupting whatever workflows had started to grow back. Higher education is a team effort. How can a team grow to strength and efficiency if it is torn apart every two years?

The process is extremely frustrating. Communication from the university leadership is poor, confused, incorrect and disrespectful. The redundancy process is carried out without any care for the impact on the employees. A university's employees are generally very smart and very motivated people, but we aren't listened to. Our thoughts are dismissed and ignored. Attempts to discuss ideas to avoid redundancies are dragged out. Little positive engagement from leadership occurs.

I resigned. I didn't do VR because I believed that my application for VR would be rejected (this is reflected in their figures on staff number reductions — my position was marked as staying). This is because I'm "cheap labour" and they needed people to stay and suffer a highly increased workload and zero research time.

Compulsory redundancies have not affected the academics so far. Professional service staff have been subjected to CR. Academics are being advised to take VES but can be declined and there is no appeal against a decline. Line managers are saying no more staff can take VES but the main University is widely advertising it. Rumours abound that CR is around the corner which would be cheaper than VES for them.

Some of us took voluntary severance deals that were contractual 15 months prior to departure. We then witnessed remaining colleagues interviewed for their jobs and ranked as gold, silver, bronze and then a number. There was no need to lose the person who has been made compulsorily redundant as there are team members who have been teaching in other teams and doing work for remission from teaching in university service and all of this has been ignored. The worst thing is that the head of department imposed on our team is not from within the subject area of the team and has no expertise or teaching in the subject yet she was deemed the subject specialist for this interview process. It is absolutely shocking to lose a teaching team member and not this head of department who is in a role and not a post as HoD who is leeching off the team and whose salary is being supported by the university whilst team members are losing jobs and being threatened. The lack of strategy about the redundancies is completely shocking and indefensible. Popular combined degrees were axed for no reason which led to the undermining of student numbers.

The redundancy letter had a very bad effect on my mental health. Made me feel useless and that I failed. Very bad impact on my family's life. I left without a job during summer time, a difficult period to look for other jobs.

I was in a pool for redundancy. It felt like the future had been taken away from me. I couldn't eat or sleep or focus on my work. My mental health deteriorated. My personal relationships were adversely affected. It was a living hell.

We were called to a meeting a month before Xmas and told they needed to reduce us in number and we were at risk of redundancy. They said decisions would be made before Xmas and staff would be leaving in January. It was incredibly stressful on top of a high work load. Tensions amongst staff were high and we were very much divided. Students picked up on the mood and were informed that they would be losing lecturers part way through the year. We had to spend the Xmas break applying for our own jobs. It impacted the whole year and former good relationships between staff were broken.

I took VSS in February 2024 under the clear impression from management that compulsory redundancy might be an option further down the line. The process was implemented at breakneck speed. I was only able to inform my students of my departure the day before I was due to leave.

The whole process was humiliating because in essence I was told that I was no longer needed, that the work I was doing, for example supervising PhDs, was of no value, that the university would take care of it, which of course it didn't. There was no consideration and empathy of any kind offered... one salary less to pay! That was all after 30 years of service!

My boss called me in for a protected conversation and told me 'if I were your age and the chance for VS came up I would strongly consider retiring.' Many over-50s, both academic and professional staff, were targeted. Some had jobs put at risk with people individually called into meetings. We were asked to make up our minds over the Easter holidays and to reply during this time if we wanted to change our minds. The whole process was very rushed. In the end over 200 staff left. The organisation was proud of itself for avoiding compulsory redundancies. The remaining staff are now having readjusted workloads and being forced to attend weekend Open Days etc., and many are now under pressure and more people off for stress.

Complete mismanagement of a redundancy process showing no regard for accepted practice or the law.

Last year we had no budget at all until after Christmas, and staff were paying for things like visiting lecturer accommodation, drinks for student exhibitions, workshop materials. When recruiting for next year's students, we were told we had to accept ALL student applicants, even if it was obvious they would not be suitable for degree study.

During the redundancy phase, the University was careful to be seen to go through consultancy meetings and score sheets that were, in reality, meaningless and degrading. They took no notice of suggestions made by staff whatsoever, so they just put everyone through three months of torment for no reason. I believe I was chosen for redundancy because I was just short of two years continuous employment so they did not need to pay me redundancy pay. They cut 10 percent of teaching and technical staff, but there were no cuts to admin, managerial staff, or those from "brand". Teams that were close were forced to compete against each other for their jobs, and a great many staff were sick because of the stress. One colleague was off for six weeks and had to take antidepressants, another was off sick with stress-related high blood pressure. I was off for two months with chest pains and work-related stress. The impact of this experience is still playing out and I am finding it very difficult to even think about looking for another job. On our programme, the remaining staff will have twice as much work to do, covering for those that have left, and yet the student numbers will be almost double. This will undoubtedly have a serious impact on the quality of delivery to the students during the 24/25 year.

Although I have not been at risk of redundancy (yet, but it is no doubt coming), I have been supporting members who have been and are currently going through the process. To put it simply, it is brutal. For the majority of members, their mental health is immediately impacted the moment they receive notification. We have had instances where management called a meeting late on a Friday afternoon of all those affected to deliver the news of the pending redundancies. Members and non-members were outraged at being delivered the news at the end of the working week as this placed them in a position where they could not access anyone for support until Monday. For those who are lucky enough to keep their jobs, if you can actually call it lucky, are left with a workload which is unsustainable. I foresee increased sickness due to work-related stress throughout this academic year as a result of teams being stretched too thin.

I was told by my then line manager that as I was not full time, that the dean considered me and others like me to be unproductive, and I had some thinking to do. I was then put on new duties that were principally administrative rather than academic, and in an academic area where I had no expertise, and admin work was piled on. I was told that this would be my job now, and my line manager took my study leave away from me - hence preventing me doing part of my role so that I could be given yet more admin. After a year of this, I took redundancy from that role when it was offered - hence I feel that I was coerced into severance by deliberately making my role so challenging.

It's been truly exhausting and disastrous for morale all around; I feel that a lot of goodwill towards senior management has been squandered, with a lack of communication all around, and months of being assured

that of course redundancies would never be considered... before the announcement of the threat of compulsory redundancy. Personally, it's made me much less willing to go the extra mile for work - why be more committed to them than they are to me? I'd like to still be the person who believes in our mission and our students enough to keep going through anything, but I don't think that's possible any more.

I have too much to say here. They've put me in a pool of one (strong case for victimisation, clearly against guidelines), where I cannot see how they can make me redundant legitimately. This makes me very anxious and is completely demotivating. We're at informal group consultancy, they've pooled by pay grade, despite no management of roles throughout my employment.

Dehumanising experience.

Having been concerned about security of my job for a couple of years in November of last year I was collectively put at risk... final paperwork for redeployment (at lower level) came through in August.

I have participated in meetings with those who are at risk of redundancy and received emails that show how distressed people are at being singled out unfairly. The Uni exec have piled costs on to departments and outlined strategies for the university their behaviour flatly contradicts.

It is completely unfair to under-resource a course or area and then criticise it for 'underperforming' when it performs brilliantly on REF and TEF criteria.

Traumatised, disheartened, and ever decreasing morale. Also, having survived the process, those of us who still remain are more overworked than ever, as a result of being further understaffed than we already were. Hard to look ahead with any sort of positivity or see any sort of future. Significant ongoing impact on both physical and mental health.

I was appointed [to a role] with an added responsibility of including [language] mentoring for students on the course, preparing to teach through the medium of [language]. Throughout the period, my grade of pay was kept as low as possible even though I was responsible for the only postgraduate course in the University College. I was subjected to continuous bullying with regard to my conducting essential components of the course through the medium of [language]. Indeed, I was prohibited from conversing with my [language] medium students within earshot of other staff, and not allowed to leave messages on noticeboards for my [language] medium students. When the University College became financially challenged, a programme of redundancies was devised, and I was immediately targeted for dismissal.

My anxiety disorder worsened significantly and I am still experiencing panic attacks. My research has stalled with the uncertainty and inability to fully plan for the future. My burnout after the redundancy process was worse than ever and I am still recovering.

I have just been 'assimilated', i.e. removed from a redundancy pool, but many of my colleagues will be made redundant after years of dedicated work and despite meeting and exceeding all expectations for their roles across teaching, admin and research/professional practice. One of the worst aspects of this experience has been silencing and self-censorship, motivated by fear. I have done my best to resist this and have been writing to external examiners, my MP in whose constituency my university also happens to be, local government, and our student union. I have also been open about my status as at risk of redundancy on social media. While it does not appear that my outspokenness has put me at a disadvantage on this occasion, other colleagues have been more hesitant to speak out, not only out of fear but, I suspect, due to a sense of shame at finding oneself in this situation. This is not our shame and we have done nothing to warrant redundancy. It is the shame of years of mismanagement, of turning universities into (poorly performing) businesses, and of politically motivated divestment from widening participation, and from the arts and humanities. As a knowledge economy migrant who came here to study and stayed to teach, I feel devastated by the academic vandalism taking place at my university and beyond. Other than vocally protesting against it, I am not sure how to fight it. We keep telling management that we as academics are overworked and abused in some respects but not consulted on matters in which we are experts, such as

student recruitment. The resource that is our experience and expertise is too often side-stepped and wasted.

Despite retaining my job, I feel like the whole process took much longer than needed (first meeting held on 10th July informing us we were all at risk of redundancy, finally being told the outcome of our reapplication and interview to retain our jobs on Monday 16th September BY EMAIL), since then, having no acknowledgement or space for airing our thoughts and feelings on the matter, or even any acknowledgment in our wider school about what had happened and who was staying (two weeks later and we are still waiting for some official communications to be sent to other staff and our students, informing them of what has happened and why half the criminology lecturers are not returning this academic year). To say this experience has impacted all of our mental and physical health is an understatement and we all feel truly undervalued and mistreated by our organisation and the senior management team.

The redundancy process was completely mishandled and management did not appear to know what they were doing. It was extremely stressful, demoralising and undermining. They did not talk to the union at first which was frustrating and infuriating. There was a lot of uncertainty over who was going to be affected and news came out gradually which exacerbated the stress. We had no real support from our line manager and it was like being cut loose to fend for ourselves, practically and emotionally. Our experience, expertise and hard work for the team was not at all valued or acknowledged. It was very isolating although the union branch did their very best - they were an amazing support and very effective in getting the management to talk to them eventually. The tone from some senior management was quite intimidating and threatening at first but they eventually started to talk to the union. At no point was I ever given an adequate reason for making my post redundant - they seemed to be making up a rationale after the decision had been made and trying to cover themselves. There was no real sense of transparency and I did not have confidence that it had been handled correctly. The option of reduced hours was discussed in detail and then dropped by senior management because it did not save enough money. It was also stressful for those staying on as the team had been decimated, leaving a bigger workload for fewer people. During this process other colleagues found alternative jobs as it was no longer an attractive place to work. I was fortunate to secure another job immediately but other colleagues took much longer to find alternative employment. It has taken a long time to get over this experience - much longer than I expected - and I now realise it has continued to affect me even one year later. Senior management at my current university have now started to discuss the potential for compulsory redundancies due to financial pressures. The sector feels like it is on its knees.

We were told just after a round of job cuts where hundreds of people lost their job that we had to have a positive attitude. That says it all.

As always, it's a false economy. Academic staff are now expected to pick up workload from administrative and technical staff made redundant, displacing revenue-generating academic work. I feel like an hourly hired taxi not a highly experienced higher-education academic. I am questioning confirmation of the date of August 2024 as the start of a pay increase as there seems to be a silence on VL contracted staff being able to claim any backdated pay rise.

The threat of redundancy is really impacting staff morale. We are anxious and stressed. We are taking on more and more workload to try to reduce the risk, but at the detriment to our own quality of teaching, mental health and student learning and the student experience

I took voluntary severance via MARS feeling that this was the best option for my sanity following persistent bullying by my director which had led to high levels of stress. The process could have helped me leave with a more positive view of the institution, however I had recently taken out a grievance against my director in view of her targeted treatment of me, and as a result of this, she granted my MARS application but treated me as though I was being dismissed, i.e., put me on garden leave with no access to IT (so disadvantaging me in finding future work), no access to other support services, no contact with colleagues and no contact from my line manager/director with the only communication channel being through HR. The University also refused to complete a notification of retirement for me. Inevitably, this has left me with

a rather sour view of my director and the organisation instead of it being a positive means of parting company after 16 years' service. In addition, my director has offered an increment to two members of my team who will each take on line management of just two of my former direct reports after I leave. Of course, I am pleased that they are being rewarded, but it hardly seems fair given that I was refused an increment despite my team having grown 4x (from seven to 28) since I was promoted to my current role in 2016.

Have kept a job but feel unsettled and anxious and also feel that if I speak out too much I will be targeted in the next round. Feel negatively affected by low morale and climate of fear all around me. Feel like I am viewed as worthless by senior managers who don't care at all about anything except keeping their friends in good positions and getting lots of money for doing hardly anything. Also feel that I am abused by managers in that because I work well they try and dump their duties onto me, resulting in more stress as I am saying no regularly in order to self-preserve. This is also a result of retaining/promoting managers who do not have appropriate skills but who are 'in with those at the top'.

I have been made redundant twice in less than 12 months. After the first redundancy, I was successful in gaining a similar position, but with increased workload. I worked up to 60-hours per week for eight months, only to be made redundant for a second time. I was awarded a new contract with reduced pay, but a similar teaching load. There are alternative ways of saving money, as our institution has spent a lot of money on new buildings, and is in stronger financial position than most other HE institutions.

I suffer from mental health issues and the threat of redundancy has exacerbated it.

[Redundancy] affect[s] morale, colleagues want to avoid you and you will be alone and waiting for [the] slaughter.

The general situation over the past 18 months has been awful. Morale has plummeted as we are constantly asked to work harder and do more with less. If this was simple incompetence on behalf of our senior leadership team, I would not mind so much. It is the sense that it is not lack of ability by these people but more an attitude of 'don't care, won't care'.

My answers relate to a current round of voluntary severance, but we had a previous round about five years ago when people were made redundant through an 'interview for your own job' process which took a huge toll on morale and health all round. The biggest toll however is that our department has lost two thirds of its staff over the last few years and we have not been allowed to hire new staff - but we are offering the same courses - so everyone is over-worked and stressed. We have just completed a new round of voluntary severance and we keep being told that the situation is dire - so hints that there is a threat to jobs are being given all the time without proper information on how this will affect individuals who have not taken voluntary severance. This causes a lot of stress and has also demotivated me entirely.

It made me question my intellectual and academic achievements. The university closed several humanities departments, including mine, Philosophy, rated as the [Xth] best in the last REF. While academic non-entities and managerial careerists kept their jobs, or were clever enough to smell the ship was sinking and left in time. The rest of us did not even receive a letter thanking us for our brilliant teaching and research.

I cannot myself provide such an account and those who have gone, are gone. I know from being a caseworker that members suffer terribly on every level. It is a war of attrition and the insane levels of aloofness from HR (solely supporting management) have prompted more than one member to observe 'I think they hope I die'/commit suicide to get rid of me'.

Workload, mistakes, and mental health problems have increased because of colleagues leaving or being made redundant.

We don't have anything specific at the moment. Employer has just announced voluntary severance scheme which is causing much anxiety and confusion amongst members. Comms have been awful and an

ill-timed announcement not detailed so we're not exactly sure what it will finally look like. On the face of it seems like they're targeting long serving staff who are very near to retirement because the offer isn't really attractive to anyone else.

Some colleagues upon hearing about leaving due to VS stopped communicating with you. Finding it difficult to remain in work with expectations to work full notice period. It's quite demoralising to try and work in a setting that feels very alienating. It's hard when you want to leave everything ok but having no one to hand over to makes this difficult. Understandably no one wants extra work but morally I believed I was helping my colleagues by volunteering for VS to save on compulsory redundancy. They don't seem to view it that way and this is leading to a very upsetting ending process for me after all the years work I have given the university.

My institution is fairly incompetent in developing a process. Every faculty is being allowed to sort its own process out and there are examples of the Dean manipulating the process to save themselves or others. There is no evidence of a process being applied to senior management or administration and no ability to think outside the box. E.g., if we are in a situation which will not allow people to go for a four-day week and be protected by doing so. Many senior staff (kids have left, mortgage paid off, etc.) could do this but it is not something that should be applied to junior staff. There are examples of particular [grade] bands being protected for no reason other than financial - there does not seem to be a level playing ground.

I actually do understand that redundancy might be unavoidable at times, for me what was unforgivable behaviour from senior management was how long the process dragged on for, with every staff member in a state of uncertainty for months and months. If redundancies are required, the decisions should be made in a timely manner, with a lot of notice to those who will be made redundant giving them good opportunity to secure alternative employment and not be left without income.

I sat in the 'consultation' meeting sobbing. No-one at the front (those consulting with us) checked on my welfare. I found colleagues distraught in their offices - again, no one had checked in on them. I haven't been able to sleep properly for the last month, my concentration has been destroyed, I haven't been able to plan or commit to anything within work or indeed outside of work. I should have been signed off work with stress but was too scared to be 'outside' of the process. After 17 years in my role I feel utterly betrayed. The way the redundancy pool was created was horribly cruel - colleagues that had high citizenship or teaching workloads ended up in the redundancy pool, essentially being punished for being collegiate. My relationship with my employer is completely broken and I don't think anything will be done to fix it. I'm scared that I will go back into the redundancy pool, but this time with a poorer redundancy offer as I have reduced my FTE.

You end up feeling like Schrödinger's Lecturer. It's hugely demotivating - why slog your guts out for work when you might not be there long enough to benefit? Why put tonnes of effort into teaching, prep, marking, when what you do might never be used again? Why plan research or other activities when you might have to take on a colleague's teaching at short notice if they take voluntary severance/redundancy? I've seen the toll it takes on morale and mental health around the department - it feels like only a matter of time before someone cracks. And it's severely impacting many colleagues' ability to research - especially those with caring responsibilities.

As stated in my grievance I feel like I had no option but to accept voluntary severance and this was due to homophobia from a student/s and bullying by a course director. [My employer] actually blamed me for the homophobia telling me I should not have spoken so much about LGBTQ issues even though I am an openly gay man teaching on a course concerning intersectionality. Meanwhile following a data access request I realised the CD had done nothing to stop the student leaving homophobic comments online and later sending homophobic emails to me.

Over 6 years, I never received a properly written contract from the university - all of them included errors, which I had to chase HR for to correct at my expense. As a BAME [Black and Minority Ethnic] person, I've experienced institutional racism (my name was constantly wrong in the university system, I experienced microaggressions on a daily basis, which senior managers treated as 'jokes' and 'humour', I wasn't offered certain opportunities available to others ("because we thought it wouldn't interest you"), my approach towards many aspects, my way of writing and culture were notoriously misunderstood or misrepresented, etc. I've also experienced the following issues: 1) I had continuous service for six years, but the university claimed that I didn't meet Regulation 8 and denied my permanency; 2) I was refused the normal annual increment to the next spine point because I was on secondment at the time, which never got corrected; 3) I had [multiple] jobs with the university ([X] academic and [X] administrative), with a separate contract for each, but the university claimed a single employment relationship and refused redundancy payment for my [...] role when the position was made redundant because I was still employed in the other roles; 4) When I was put at risk as [role] and found a job that could become my redeployment, it took the university half a year to agree the decision, as a result of which I missed on academic salary protection 5) I was unfairly dismissed as [role] (the university made my position redundant and then employed somebody else for lower pay to do my job). I disputed all these issues with the university for two years and became so unwell as a result that I developed severe anxiety and panic attacks. I eventually had a nervous breakdown and sought the help of a psychiatrist, who stated that I had a completely deregulated nervous system. The two-year battle with the university also ruined my relationship and my partner left me because I was constantly stressed, couldn't sleep, and had panic attacks, and he couldn't stand it.

Each year, as a department we have increasing numbers of UG [undergraduate] students, but have simultaneously lost staff due to hiring freezes and voluntary redundancy. School management also imposed a ban on hiring temporary teaching staff (including for PGRs [postgraduates]) in the dept. So teaching workloads for remaining teaching staff has increased quite heavily.

While I have long known that universities do not value academic staff, part of me was still shocked to be reduced so starkly to simply a 'cost-benefit' equation, to my cash worth to the institution. Along with a lack of transparency about the rationale for decisions taken about which role profiles were placed at 'risk', communication was consistently insensitive and unclear. All of us spent a great deal of time and energy simply trying to establish the realities of the process and our rights/situation. This was ongoing over weeks and weeks. Being placed at risk of redundancy and the mishandling of the process took a huge toll on my mental (and physical) health. This toll has never been adequately acknowledged by my head of school, let alone by the institution. I was placed in direct competition with a small number of colleagues, some of whom I have worked with for many years. It was heartbreaking to see the impact on them. While there were (officially) no compulsory redundancies, I am sure that many colleagues felt 'pushed out' and took voluntary redundancy because they did not feel safe. We lost over 200 colleagues. There has been no aftercare process and it seems I am expected to simply pick up where I left off with no acknowledgment of the trauma inflicted by the process and the impact this has had on my working and personal life. Workloads have increased and colleagues feel insecure. Senior management have refused to engage with union questions about their responsibility for poor financial management. The whole redundancy process was dehumanising, it has left me burnout and demoralised.

The divisional senior leadership team has cited financial constraints as a justification for bullying and threatening staff. This rationale has also been used to increase workloads. I have experienced a 75% increase in my teaching load, largely due to unfilled vacancies resulting from the recruitment freeze and the lack of temporary staff. This situation has significantly impacted the mental and physical well-being of the staff.

Staggering in my own case. My own school was merged with a school that was having significant financial difficulties and I ended up losing my job, despite being a high performer on their metrics. Basically if you are the wrong cell on a spreadsheet then you are gone - simple as that. HR start to treat you as the enemy. I asked detailed questions about the case for my redundancy - all of which were ignored - the default HR answer is "the computer says no." It is a brutal process and one you have zero control over.

Extreme stress and did not feel listened to at all. Shady practices by HR. Clear breaches of legislation. Bullying from 'safe' colleagues.

Fake redundancy process, in the end no-one was made redundant, but staff were reappointed to a lower pay grade. Very stressful for all concerned. Appropriate procedure not followed.

I have been through a similar experience 20 years ago at the same institution but the cuts this time were deeper and affected the whole University. A whole grade band was removed with all PLs threatened with compulsory redundancies. Alternative posts such as SLs were not planned to be offered due to a 20-month pay-protection policy. The experience was harrowing, felt profoundly unfair after staff on those grades had successfully led the whole portfolio redesign for their respective departments. Staff who were part of the pool were subjected to painful and non-standard interviews to obtain Associate Head's posts which replaced some of the PLs. Seeing approximately 120 academic colleagues leave the University between April and August due to opting for VSS or VR was harrowing, and followed by a further 300 professional services staff. For those of us forced to take alternative SL posts, offered in some areas due to significant staff shortages, the demotion after many years of performing successfully at PL level is demoralising, a source of constant psychological distress and career-limiting. Many colleagues had/are planning to leave academia altogether.

It has been profoundly stressful and has undermined my confidence in my ability to do my job. There is no clear vision or plan for the future and for researchers and tutors. Once a project or contract ends those on managerial level simply do know what to do or expect. Moreover, I experienced the redundancy process during pregnancy and I can firmly say that the new redundancy law for new and expectant parents (2024) is not respected and the so called "suitable job alternative" is a grey area and lacks of internal policies. The employer failed to provide suitable alternatives even when the same grade posts were advertised. The process is unfair as the employer requires pregnant employees to apply normally (for lower or same grades) and do not guarantee the priority status. Once I asked for clarification, they were very vague and often appealed to essential criteria that were not originally in the job description. I was hit with a protected conversation and an offer of MARs voluntary scheme payment to leave end of the month, on the basis they were going to recommend my role for redundancy anyway. I'd suspected something like this was going to happen as my line manager and executive I worked for had bullied and excluded me suddenly for 18 months with no reason or explanation, I wasn't told I'd done anything wrong, their behaviour just became toxic and got worse over time. I refused the severance offer as I knew I had protected pension rights so would benefit from redundancy so made them take me through the process. Their dreadful behaviour continued to the end. I got an interview for a lower graded role through redeployment which was withdrawn the night before interview and no suitable explanation was given. This was weeks before the end of my consultation so I ended up raising a grievance and then they offered me a redundancy package to avoid going to employment tribunal but gave me the redundancy reason needed to ensure my pension benefits were protected. The union were fantastic and did everything they could but were up against people who wanted me to leave and not be redeployed. The union couldn't understand if the [institution] was being incompetent or if it was victimisation, I know for a fact from the evidence I logged and from the SAR I submitted that it was definitely 100% victimisation! And this was from the very top, so sanctioned behaviour and approach. I secured a new job to go straight into and four months on I realise how toxic and awful the culture is at the [university] and it starts at the top!

I have worked at two institutions in [city]. The first had me on a zero hours contract that was not renewed, the second has had compulsory redundancies. I had a temporary contract and was told that ALL temporary contracts would not be renewed but this was untrue. There are no jobs here in the sector now, and at least 40 staff looking for them. My MP was not in the least interested and neither were the local press - even with so many out of work. One of the institutions did not admit the job cuts publicly and glossed it over for students.

Anxiety, stress, depression or other health problems. A cold awareness that all contributions made, all the good work done, all the students taught and supervised successfully, all the pastoral care provided, and all the profit generated, over decade(s) by colleagues are dismissed in an instant once executive

management sees the opportunity to cut expenses (i.e. staff) to safeguard their own pay and bonuses. Apparently, it is never poor management that led to a situation where deficits arise, but poor teaching and research staff performance, or acts of God (or perhaps excessive rain?).

I just feel completely cut off from my old institution and from access to resources and funding to carry on research and publishing. My whole department didn't seem to care when I left my role - everyone is too worried that they will be next. Morale is very low, and it's really hard to keep motivated.

Two members of my department of 14 were fired (or in fact, forced to resign rather than be fired) in 2011. This affected me psychologically, as it gave me a feeling of impermanence, and that the employer was hostile and might use any perceived underperformance (e.g., in numbers of publications) to fire me. It was also completely without logic, too, as within a couple of years the department had hired new staff in the same areas. One colleague forced to leave was in her early 50s and has never worked again.

I am over 50. Our group was targeted for redundancy and we were told our group was at risk and applications for VS invited. In some cases 'protected' conversations were held with individuals and the time taken to make such a life-changing decision was very short. In some cases the pensions department was overwhelmed as people tried to find out how they stood re taking early USS pensions, etc. The unions were not consulted properly. As a committee member I took part in casework and attended some of these meetings to make sure people were treated fairly. On one case an employee was told 'well as you are over 50 I would jump at the chance if it were me'. This manager was in their mid-40s! People were very demoralised and felt they had no choice but to apply for VS. In the end the University management prides itself on the fact that there were no compulsory redundancies. But the people left behind have increased workloads and are expected to attend weekend open days etc., the atmosphere for those that remain is toxic. It makes you feel like a failure - like your career is suddenly going to end without an opportunity to continue to develop or build on your achievements. It also makes you question decisions you made about choosing particular employers or beat yourself up about having a better track record to insulate yourself from redundancy. Finally, you realise how precarious your standard of living and ability to provide for your family are.

A redundancy procedure in a completely unrelated department caused fear, stress and distress in my own department. Staff (rightly on the facts) didn't believe that it was due to lack of student recruitment; they felt the university was looking to cut costs. Staff were also much less willing to assert their contractual rights (e.g., max teaching loads, max working hours, weekend teaching only by agreement, etc.) because they felt it would lead to them being targeted for redundancy.

Felt targeted for redundancy because of menopause by male managers.

Being targeted for compulsory redundancy out of the blue was incredibly stressful and demoralising. The data used to argue for staff cuts was deeply flawed but senior management would not accept our detailed responses to the so-called 'consultation'. The only way our team managed to avoid two of us being forced out was by collectively agreeing to reduce our fractions. This has left us effectively doing the same job for substantially less money. I have no faith left in my employer and not much left in the wider sector as a whole. As a result I am seriously considering leaving the profession which I have spent over 15 years building a place within. The way it is being done is so upsetting, since no regard is being given to what is needed to run the course properly, or to the knowledge and skills of those who are currently doing it, or to what will happen afterwards. The staff team has been totally decimated and all the good practice and results built up over the years just rubbished. One comment was that the course doesn't require the level of seniority held by existing staff - this is a team with very little turnover and most are SL. They are totally committed and extremely good at problem solving, but there was no dialogue, just a management proposal that included demotion and turning the few remaining posts into FT. Most staff are fractional since they are professional creatives in their own right, which makes for excellent teachers. There was such a cynical response to the staff counter-proposal, that addressed none of the points made, and proceeded to make more drastic cuts - and they called it consultation!

The redundancy process destroyed my faith in the institution I worked for and whose ethos I had publicised and promoted widely. The fully committed approach to my work seemed to have been completely undermined and being within the redundancy pool showed me that there was no consideration of how important I had been to the institution. The redundancy of many colleagues (voluntary and compulsory) affected my ability to do my job and reduced morale widely. Confidence and hope is returning now that significant management figures have departed the university.

I (obviously) am not party to the detail of the finances but it seems that in order to save money on a spreadsheet, the University has taken very short term action that will have long-term consequences (cost of everything, value of nothing approach). Workloads will increase, not just in teaching but in ancillary tasks that will worsen experience, National Student Survey will again be poor and we will fail to recruit to our targets. Some financial pain is necessary if we don't want to go off a cliff edge of poor service. I cannot speak for everyone but what I have observed and in some cases experienced was that those on precarious, temporary or fixed term contracts have faced the sabotaging of future employment opportunities, constructive dismissal, bullying and harassment, discrimination, abuse of probationary periods and lack of agency around accepting and managing workload. This has led to reduced morale among the cohort and spending precious time seeking employment elsewhere. It is detrimental to health and overall work-life balance. There is an attitude of assuming that fixed-term contracts will never be renewed and there will never be another position, so those on fixed-term contracts should plan to look elsewhere when their contract ends. When there are new positions available these are not consistently shared and who shares them is also inconsistent. Those in precarious contracts and especially migrants whose visas depend on employer sponsorship and regular check-ins with the Home Office risk both their employment and their residence in the United Kingdom if faced with repercussions as a result of voicing their concerns. Generally turnover, among other things, has reduced diversity and inclusivity, which is difficult for both staff who leave and for those who remain.

I was put at risk in a pool of one in 2023. The reason given was that I was under hours for teaching. I was the lead Professor and was awarded [X hours of] remission for research and a further [X] hours for leading on a major university funding bid with huge national recognition. As a result my teaching contact time was significantly reduced by the design of SMT. When the bid was unsuccessful both packages of remission were withdrawn without my knowledge. In the month before the at-risk notice, I had discussed my position with the Provost who had told me I wasn't 'his kind of professor' as I hadn't brought much funding in and wasn't in the media enough, so he was finding it hard to make a business case for me. So I sent him a full breakdown of the millions I had brought in, the project bids I was working on and their value, along with a copy of a weekly magazine supplement that had just run a feature on me, and files of the numerous radio shows and podcasts I'd recently been a guest on. He ignored it and refused to meet with me to discuss my business case. I was subsequently systematically removed from all committees and all responsibilities as part of an internal 'restructure'. During the last strikes the same Provost took the names of all of the staff on the picket line. I was there as an active union member and the [X] officer. So the 'at-risk' notice was no surprise! After the first at-risk meeting I contacted colleagues to secure extra teaching and managed to make up the shortfall. I also discovered that the work planning document HR was working from didn't include my PhD dissertation supervisions, so my solution would potentially put me over hours. The Head of School who was conducting the meetings rejected this as a 'redeployment' solution as he already 'had plans to cover those teaching hours'. I was offered no other redeployment. Bottom line, I was the most expensive person in his school and he had savings to make. I took 'voluntary' redundancy but was hurried by HR to make my decision as they had a deadline, which was ahead of the time period for the process. Basically they wanted me out of the building before the new VC arrived. I left on the day before he started. The entire process was among the most dehumanising and isolating experiences of my life. I was already struggling with my mental health due to a recent neurodiversity diagnosis, which I'd shared with the Head of School and HR not long before the at-risk meeting was called. It left me with a deep loss of self-worth. I was made to feel that all of my work had been for nothing. I suffered depression, total loss of any confidence in my abilities. This seriously impacted on my job search, and I ended up taking a job two-and-a-half hours away from where I live at a much lower pay-scale. My new university, [X] Uni is now in a process of restructuring. The long-term impact of the redundancy process I experienced, my diagnosis and

the subsequent reduction in job role status resulted in numerous issues for me settling in to my new job as an Assistant Professor (senior lecturer in old money). I also discovered my new place of employment was toxic. Bullying is the norm. While this is something I have been able to deal with effectively in the past, post-redundancy I lost the confidence to challenge. I am now in the most desperate situation I have ever been in. I've lost all confidence in my abilities and face bullying from my line manager as a daily occurrence.

I fully blame the redundancy process at [X] University for my state of mind, my poor mental health and loss of self-confidence. And to add insult to injury, during the at-risk meetings I was told the Provost had agreed to my being awarded Emeritus Professor. That was 18 months ago, and they still haven't confirmed in writing. It has created a horrible atmosphere of uncertainty, where people have been worried about talking to colleagues because no-one knows who is staying or going. In theory, colleagues are pitted against each other because they can suggest someone else should be made redundant instead of them. Negotiations are inconsistent across the university and we have lost friends and colleagues, some of whom left good jobs a short time ago to come and work here. The result is that some people are pushed out inexplicably and the rest have to pick up their work, despite already working at capacity. Meanwhile, senior management continues to grow as the VC brings in his friends to well paid jobs. Something's not right but it's a closed shop there and they aren't open to any discussions or negotiations on anything. Should we just be grateful for a job? That's the way it feels.

Being at risk for of redundancy for over six months approx. five years ago has had lasting negative impacts on my mental health - a post-traumatic stress disorder response is now apparent when the possibility of cuts raises its head. Anxiety goes through the roof.

The redundancy process at [institution] was typical of its vacillation about decisive action as it has been a process that has gone on indefinitely and could have been better served by making firm decisions about closing programmes, rather than a death by a thousand cuts which has seen staff (including myself) who could not stand the toxicity of the place leave. Colleagues are left to continue teaching with a much reduced staff (my department, already small, lost two very experienced staff with major admin roles, leaving three full-time lecturers and one fractional). It would have been kinder, if brutal, to have closed the programme, enabling us all to teach it out (and someone like me close but not close enough to retirement to earn a full-time salary for three further years).

Our redundancies were handled in such a way that colleagues had a good deal of uncertainty about the future of their jobs, but more importantly the trust in the University hierarchy was severely damaged. This led to a lot of good staff leaving and finding posts elsewhere, while others took voluntary severance. We have lost, in particular, a lot of programme directors and heads of department and this has placed significant pressure on those staff who remain.

Redundancies at our university have impacted the student experience and given our current financial situation further cuts seem likely. This has definitely affected staff and student morale.

The overall atmosphere is pretty grim. Services are decimated by VS/VR which affects the quality of work of everybody left. Various of the people remaining are looking for alternative jobs. Our university has given a pompous name to the process of reshaping the work and workload of who is left which — de facto — amounts to covering holes, more workload, less freedom on how to do the work (less academic freedom) and, in the end, less services for staff and students. Everybody is demoralised.

I was put at risk of redundancy in 2021 because of course closures. The department affected had a high proportion of active union members (including a large number of branch committee members) and staff had been highly vocal in criticising the direction and management of the university, so we think it had been targeted for political reasons and not merely for the stated reason of supposedly poor student recruitment. In the end, I was not made redundant (though several of my colleagues took voluntary severance - in effect 'voluntary' only in name) but I was redeployed to another department. The entire experience was incredibly stressful and has set back my academic career: I have become deeply depressed,

and disillusioned with the university and academia in general, and consider that what had been a successful career has now been derailed.

I've been through the restructuring process at [university] twice - in 2022-23 (after which I was been offered a fractional post, and starting from September 2024 (again, put at risk of redundancy). I think it's the worst job experience of my whole life and career and, taking more generally, it's ruining the international reputation of the UK HE sector. I have taught in the EU, and internationally, and have never heard of such catastrophic, industrial scale of redundancies in any other country, totally disrespectful to academics, researchers and educators, producers of knowledge, culture and civility. It's totally barbaric! The UCU should be more active and militant before it's too late, and also take the discussion to the national level.

My colleagues' current experience is that we might face CR and are being offered VR to avoid this. We seem to be in a liminal space where we are being told we are not at the CR stage yet, and we are being asked to give feedback on the shoddy business case for the CR. That being said, the main message from the university is that we cannot confirm or deny anything at the moment, while the UCU seems to be in the dark (or slightly less in the dark than before and is encouraging people in affected departments to be pro-active in giving feedback questioning the legitimacy of the process). However, all this feels like fighting with fog(!), we don't know what we are fighting, we don't know how long we'll have to sit in this halfway stage and we don't feel that we can land a punch in our defence. It is having an impact on morale, stress and anxiety. This is my personal opinion, and this is only my own, I feel that even those people that survive this CR process (if it happens?) will have had their faith in the institution rocked to its core. They won't want to stay long, and they will be looking for an exit strategy unless they need to hang on in here until retirement. No one will ever be able to see their long-term career here, because they feel that the way the university has dealt with this situation has been shocking, inept and a betrayal.

It happened a long time ago (2016), so I no longer seek aftercare; and I was actually relieved to stop working at [institution], so didn't resist the redundancy/severance bullying as much I might (or should) have done... but the process adopted by the managers involved was also overwhelmingly effective at defying any resistance on my part, or on the part of the union; I was thoroughly disempowered by the steps they took, and this was, to me, clearly their intention, either because of my activity as a union officer, or for some other reason which was never disclosed. [Authors' note: while this respondent was made redundant in 2016, they work at an institution that was/is experiencing job cuts within the survey's period of interest].

Devaluing, and degrading. Our entire department was forced to re-apply for our jobs in a process that ranges from late April 2024, culminating in late July, and we lost people through CR as a part of this process. It was a desktop exercise on the part of management, so outside of the sham consultation process, colleagues had no voice.

I have seen members of staff—some with nearly forty years of experience—bullied and “worked on” by management until they either took voluntary severance when offered or otherwise went off sick for months and then quit. The current incarnation of the workload system at [X] University is particularly exacting. It was revised in about 2016 to diminish the hours for preparation and other things. It is wielded like a blunt instrument against us (80% under the current workload is more than we were asked to do prior to 2016). Most of us are now at 100% or more and many are going off sick with nervous breakdowns, which pushes more work onto others who remain, who then go off sick. There is a freeze on hiring and promotions and an atmosphere of fear and intimidation for any who do not toe the line. I love this university but despise its hateful, greedy and mostly incompetent leadership. If I had an option to leave, I would take it now.

Seeing friends and colleagues that are foundational to the success of the University take voluntary severance is painful. The best staff leave and the remaining staff are expected to pick up the slack. Now in the 3rd round of VS, the pressure has increased beyond levels anyone can stand. We still have the same

amount of hours in a day and the increasing workload is unmanageable. When this is raised we are told to just get on with it and the very real concerns about physical and mental health are largely ignored. Staff have all been pushed together into one building meaning staff are being pitted against staff for dwindling resources. Training opportunities are offered but pulled away at the last moment to appear like the offer is there but in reality it was never an option. Those paid the most seem to retain their jobs whilst those paid the least are not being rehired. Their work doesn't disappear nor get officially redistributed. Just given to or expected to be covered by remaining staff.

I have had over 15 contracts at the same institute over the last five years. I have experienced high job insecurity and institutionalised inequality while evidently performing at global top level. My ideas were stolen by more senior academics in other institutes and my work gets continuously plagiarised. I was bullied, discriminated against, and my boundaries were crossed with inappropriate sexual behaviour. I was promised promotions and then denied, often due to failing and [opaque?] administrative procedures, resulting in countless redundancy processes. Having done my time, I was given a "permanent" contract, which allowed me to buy a house and move forward a little in my life. To my surprise I was then invited for an end of contract review, because according to the university the funding that supported my contract came to an end - exactly like it was with fixed term contracts. This was hugely stressful and also incorrect, because I had funds for my own and my team's continued employment. My contract could be saved after putting up another fight, and I also was awarded promotion. However, according to the university, and due to a hiring freeze, there is no position for me to move into, so I am facing redundancy again. My mental health has greatly suffered, having depression and anxiety. My physical health deteriorated, accelerating chronic illness.

I have heard about colleagues on visas that they feel especially threatened because depending on their visa arrangements, they may have very limited time to leave the country (including taking kids out from school, arranging relocation, etc.) if they are being made redundant.

Very disrespectful and undermining.

When I was made redundant in 2020, I was told for upwards of six months not to worry about how a restructure would impact me, until my role was listed as one of only two Professional Services roles that were to be eliminated. In the weeks prior to this, both managers in my department cornered me and told me I should look for a job elsewhere, without explaining any further detail. There were other instances in which one or both managers isolated me, misinformed me, and then subsequently lied about what they had told me. I then was offered interview for the role that was to replace mine, for which I was vastly overqualified simply by virtue of being an internal candidate with experience in the specialised department, to say nothing of my actual extensive expertise. I was asked in interview to list materials which I happened to know would vary and never remain static, and which I would always be given a list of for provisions in advance; I am confident this was an interview question provided by my manager specifically to undermine my neurodiversity accommodation, and to target my lack of experience in clinical care, when the role was not dedicated to that but equally weighted on public health, in which I have years of experience and expertise. The post which replaced mine, for which I was overqualified and yet unsuccessful in interview, then remained vacant for over two years. I know my union reps were deeply disappointed with this outcome, as they had been assured the interview was simply a formality and I was obviously the best candidate for the role. I also know that another member of my team was targeted and bullied both in the lead-up and after my redundancy, and I believe voluntarily resigned from post later the same year.

Redundancy sprung on us completely out of the blue that a restructure was happening and certain jobs would not be needed. Less than 24 hours' notice, no right to representation and clearly not following University policies or consultation with the Branch. The treatment of long-serving staff, without a blemish over many years of service is disgusting and typical of a transactional management culture. We have also been party to an increasingly toxic environment of being sidelined, marginalised with persistent low level bullying over a number of months by management. The immediate health impacts, both physical and mental have been devastating already. Not everyone has access to a good support network due to their

personal circumstances. I cannot imagine dealing with this situation without union support. Those of us affected believe we have been subject to growing 'cancellation' and singled out for not always agreeing with less than transparent management decisions.

It was soul destroying.

I took a VES in April before the current 100+ compulsory redundancies in academic staff were announced. This ended a very poor 10-year experience at the university over which I was continually negatively targeted by middle management (so-called 'Heads of School', etc.). I had had a 40-year career and was one of the most cited staff in my recent University - certainly the top achiever in my discipline. Following instances of poor management and leadership by HoD and HoS I had raised legitimate issues with the Dean etc., especially about health and safety on field trips, offered solutions and suggestions to improve matters and indicated I would help wherever I could. For my efforts I was then viciously turned on by an incompetent HoS who tried to orchestrate a baseless disciplinary action. To that date, I had had a blemishless career and was highly respected in my field both nationally and internationally. Additionally, our UG student discipline recruitment had fallen by 75% in four years so the writing was on the wall anyway. The offered VES terms came along shortly after the threats against me were dropped; these VES terms were good and by this stage I'd had enough of the back-stabbing and stress anyway. To be honest I was relieved to leave and retire early and the process was completed efficiently in less than a month - apparently so the University books could be balanced within the tax year. I have found adjusting to life outside academia difficult, and feel I have largely left all I had achieved behind.

The voluntary redundancy scheme was open over the summer with zero communication from line manager about how many staff had opted for the scheme. We had three colleagues take VS and coupled with the departures of over a dozen staff from the department in recent years (the majority of those appointments have not been re-recruited - including two Professor positions and two Readers). Work has simply be redistributed amongst the skeletal staff - with increased student numbers the pressure is immense. The university have just announced they will be cutting significant academic jobs in the faculty. What is particularly bruising here is they are forcing through programme (entire undergraduate degree) re-writes within weeks on top of current workloads. The same week it was announced that the university would be dismantling part of one of the main buildings within which the faculty of humanities is housed. Apparently we need newer facilities to attract students. With the staff working as hard as they are the levels of anxiety and infighting have increased significantly. It's making a difficult workplace unbearable.